

D4.2

Final report on interviews conducted and research findings

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Partner abbreviations	Full name
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway)
HI	Háskóli Íslands (University of Iceland)
LOBA	Loba (Portugal)
CHX	Crowd Helix (Ireland)
SVEN	Smart Venice (Italy)
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Abbreviations

Meaning

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIDP	Associazione Italiana Direttori del Personale
AIWM	Artificial Intelligence Worker Management
ANT	Actor-network Theory
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CSO	Civil Society Organization
CTO	Chief Technology Officer
CV	Curriculum vitae
DEI	Diversity, Equality, Inclusion
HR	Human Resources
HRM	Human Resources Management
MS	Microsoft
SME	Small Medium Size Enterprise
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

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1 Executive Summary

This report describes the extensive work done in the *BIAS: mitigating biases of AI in the labour market-project* in Work Package 4 on qualitative SSH research. It starts with a recap on Stage 1 qualitative data collection also described in the report D4.1 done before summer 2024. We then describe the qualitative data collection of Stage 2 done in autumn 2024, as well as the analytical steps that have been taken (and are still ongoing) up until 31st March 2025, when this report was made available for internal review. We then finally describe the upcoming work for the last period of the work package to happen from April 2025 until the end of the project, which will be subject to the future deliverable D4.3, to be submitted April 2026.

2 Introduction to qualitative SSH research in bias

Bias in AI-driven recruitment and management processes are increasingly recognized as a complex sociotechnical issue that extends beyond technical flaws. While much of the existing research on AI bias focuses on quantitative and computational methods to measure and mitigate bias, qualitative Social Science and Humanities (SSH) research offers crucial complementary insights into the social, cultural, and ethical dimensions of AI recruitment. Qualitative SSH methodologies in bias research thus help emphasize the contribution to understanding human-AI interactions, decision-making processes, and systemic inequalities in digital hiring and management. Traditional approaches to bias in AI recruitment rely heavily on quantitative methods, such as statistical audits, bias detection algorithms, and fairness metrics (Binns, 2020; Mehrabi et al., 2021). While these methods are essential for identifying patterns and disparities, they often fail to capture the underlying social dynamics and lived experiences of individuals affected by AI-driven hiring systems (D'Ignazio & Klein, 2020). Summarized, qualitative SSH research helps fill this gap by:

- Contextualizing bias by examining how bias emerges through organizational practices, social norms, and decision-making processes rather than solely within algorithmic outputs (Barocas et al., 2019).
- Exploring lived experiences by investigating how job applicants, recruiters, and HR professionals perceive and interact with AI recruitment technologies (Raghavan et al., 2020).
- Uncovering structural and cultural factors by identifying how historical, cultural, and economic conditions shape biases in hiring (Eubanks, 2018).
- Critiquing the assumptions of AI systems by questioning the underlying logic of AI-driven recruitment tools, including how concepts like “merit” and “fairness” are operationalized (Benjamin, 2019).
- Highlighting challenges and risks to employees’ health and well-being alongside AI worker management (Christenko et.al. 2022).

By moving beyond statistical measurements of bias, qualitative SSH research enables a deeper, more nuanced understanding of how bias manifests at multiple levels—from individual experiences to institutional practices. The importance of SSH research in AI governance has been recognized by international policy bodies and funding agencies, including the European Commission (2020), UNESCO (2021), and the OECD (2022). SSH disciplines contribute to:

- Developing ethical guidelines for AI recruitment (European Commission, 2019).
- Informing legal and regulatory frameworks on AI fairness and transparency (Mittelstadt et al., 2016).
- Ensuring AI systems align with human rights and democratic values (Crawford, 2021).

By integrating qualitative SSH insights into AI governance, policymakers and developers can create more inclusive and equitable hiring technologies that go beyond technical fixes to address deep-rooted social inequalities. By combining SSH knowledge with other disciplinary knowledge from computer science, law, and other STEM based disciplines we can get a more holistic understanding of problems arising with AI development and use, as well as potential solutions and mitigation strategies.

2.1 A sociotechnical understanding of AI technology

A sociotechnical perspective on AI management and recruitment systems recognizes that these technologies do not operate in isolation but are embedded within complex networks of human, organizational, and technical interactions. From this perspective, AI is not merely a neutral tool that automates hiring decisions; rather, it is an active participant in a web of human and institutional influences (MacKenzie & Wajcman, 1999; Suchman, 2007), as well as a potent tool for managing workers (Christenko et al., 2022; Kim and Bodie, 2021; Robert et al., 2020). To further understand this, three key sociotechnical dimensions of AI bias in management and recruitment are particularly important for the BIAS project:

Human-Algorithm Interaction:

- AI-driven hiring tools rely on human inputs, including training data, algorithmic design choices, and system configurations (Binns, 2019). However, these inputs are shaped by existing social hierarchies, implicit biases, and cultural assumptions (Crawford, 2021).
- Recruiters often trust AI systems as objective decision-makers, but studies suggest that AI-generated rankings and scores influence human evaluators in ways that reinforce bias rather than eliminate it (Raghavan et al., 2020).
- AI-based algorithms, and their possible negative consequences seem strong (Bailey, 2022) as Artificial Intelligence Worker Management (AIWM) challenges the wellbeing, health and safety of workers and is considered by some as unethical, intrusive and stressful (Moore, 2018; De Stefano, 2020; Gal et al. 2020; Christenko et al. 2022).

Institutional and Organizational Embedding of AI Systems:

- AI recruitment and management tools are adopted within specific organizational cultures, where pre-existing norms around diversity, fairness, and efficiency shape how these systems are deployed, shaping the social construction of technology (Bailey, 2022; Barocas et al., 2019; Bijker, 1995; De Stefano, 2020).
- Even when designed with fairness in mind, AI systems may reinforce historical hiring patterns that favor certain groups over others due to biased organizational data (Ajunwa, 2020).

Power Structures and the Politics of AI Recruitment and Management:

- AI hiring technologies often claim neutrality and fairness, but decisions about who gets interviewed, shortlisted, or hired remain subject to opaque decision-making processes controlled by developers and employers (Benjamin, 2019).
- The governance of AI recruitment and management is shaped by legal, ethical, and corporate interests, often sidelining job seekers who have limited agency in challenging AI-driven hiring decisions (Mittelstadt et al., 2016; De Stefano, 2020).

By applying a sociotechnical framework, qualitative SSH research reveals that bias in AI hiring, and management is not simply a computational problem—it is a deeply social phenomenon that emerges through complex entanglements of technology, institutions, and human decision-making. Qualitative SSH research thus plays a critical role in the study of bias in AI recruitment and management, offering rich, context-sensitive insights that complement quantitative approaches. By examining lived experiences, cultural dynamics, and organizational practices, SSH methodologies provide a more comprehensive understanding of how and why bias persists in AI hiring and management tools. As AI recruitment continues to expand, interdisciplinary collaboration between SSH, STEM, and legal scholars will be essential to developing fair, transparent, and accountable hiring systems.

3 AI bias in recruitment

The focus for the SSH work has been AI bias in recruitment. We first show the original literature review from D4.1, before adding novel insights into the literature since then. In D4.1 we wrote:

“AI systems have since their beginnings been dealing with the concept of “bias” (Jirauch, 1966, Caruana & Schaffer, 1988; Haussler, 1988). Bias in AI can be understood in several ways, e.g. as a preference to certain data, procedural workings, or outcomes of models. Hellström et al. (2020) in their paper “Bias in Machine Learning--What is it Good for?” e.g. describe how “different types of biases are connected and depend on each other” stating that there is “a complex relation between bias occurring in the machine learning pipeline that leads to a model, and the eventual bias of the model (which is typically related to social discrimination). The former bias may or may not influence the latter, in a sometimes bad, and sometime good way.” From a political side, Podesta’s (2014) White House report warning against the negative implications of Big Data technologies, as well as the European “Assessment list for Trust-worthy Artificial Intelligence “(ALTAI) published in 2018, by the European Commission’s High-Level Expert Group on AI, setting guidelines for AI has warned against harmful impacts. Discrimination in AI has been investigated by scholars from diverse disciplines. The discriminatory potential of and/or practices around these technologies have e.g. been studied in risk assessment for criminal recidivism (Angwin et al., 2016; Courtland, 2018; Green, 2018) and for custodial decisions (Burgess, 2018), healthcare (Birzhandi and Cho, 2023), in public personnel management (Cho et. al. 2023), and in hiring algorithms (Bogen and Rieke 2018). Multiple studies point to the fact that algorithmic bias may either amplify existing bias, as in the case of Conditional Random Field (CRF) (Zhao 2017) or credit scoring systems (Hurlin et al., 2021) or create new types of bias, as in the case of COMPAS risk assessment (Brackey, 2019) or risk adjustment (RA) models (Zink and Rose, 2021).

A recent scoping review conducted as part of the BIAS project shows how the use of AI in recruitment and HRM includes “outreach, screening, assessment and coordination” (Rigotti and Fosch-Villaronga, 2024, 2), highlighting how AI can outperform humans in the screening process and enhance their performance in assessment and process coordination. On the other side, Black and Van Esch (2020), underline the growing importance of intangibles to the economy and hence the centrality of recruitment as a “top strategic concern” (p. 216), assert that it has now become essential for companies to use AI in recruitment, which they call Digital Recruiting 3.0. They argue that analogue recruiting, which relied solely on humans in the recruitment process, was plagued by anchoring, confirmation and similarity biases, which were assumed – though not proven – to be mitigated by the Digital Recruiting 3.0 turn. A recent umbrella review of the literature on AI use in recruitment indeed highlights a broad consensus that “AI has the potential to mitigate discrimination in personnel selection,” as it is “perceived to be more fair and objective in comparison to hiring decisions based on human judgment”, a conviction endorsed across AI industry marketing, the HRM literature, and discussions surrounding AI ethics (Seppala and Malecka, 2024).

Yet, Seppala and Malecka (2024) assert that this belief mostly stems from depending on presumed “specific meanings of the concepts of rationality, bias, fairness, objectivity and AI” which the industry “accept as self-evident” (p.1, 3), and which are otherwise quite debatable. Looking back at initiatives to reduce BIAS, such as the ALTAI model (Ala-Pietilä et al. 2020), there are several initiatives both for use and improvement. Radclyffe et al. (2023) argues that political bodies and industry have a special responsibility for ALTAI to be widely adopted. Gavornik et al. (2022) e.g. suggests stakeholder involvement as a way to improve the model. The BIAS project is focused on conducting continued research into the different conceptions of bias, fairness, objectivity and other related concepts for different actors in different contexts, and what the involvement of AI in these contexts means to them.”

Since the publication of D4.1, several new insights have appeared in the literature. Mori et al. (2024) expanded research by conducting a literature review of scholarly articles dealing with AI in recruitment, focusing in particular on the different ethical theories applied. Their research first identifies 2020 as a crucial year for AI in recruitment due to the increased digitalization imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic. Since then, an increasing number of scholars dealt with this topic and explored the use of AI in HRM. The main understanding of AI in recruitment is through the utilitarian lens, arguing that AI will make recruitment more efficient and more objective. The justice view, on the other hand, focuses on the risks of algorithmic bias and reflects on the candidate’s well-being, while the rights view focuses on compliance with the legal frameworks surrounding AI use in the workplace. The fact that the utilitarian view is the most common in Mori et al.’s review is quite concerning, as it overlooks issues of bias and ethical decision making in recruitment which might be better achieved through an integration of all three approaches. This finding reflects Seppala and Malecka’s (2024) research of AI companies’ narratives which revolve around a utilitarian view of AI as more efficient, objective, and neutral while overlooking the complexity of concepts such as bias, fairness, or objectivity. Scholars and HR practitioners continue to adopt a utilitarian view to the use of AI in HR (Purohit and Banerjee, 2025; Almeida et al., 2025) which makes more intersectional research necessary.

Based on the previous research, scholars further investigated the ethical aspects and called for empirical research regarding AI in recruitment. Drag and Mackereth (2022) analyzed marketing and promotional materials from developer company that produce AI tools for recruitment, arguing that their promise of debiased solutions in fact fail to address the systemic inequality in the organizations, thus exacerbating the unfair treatment towards job candidates. Building on an ethnography on HR department in an international organization, van den Broek et al. (2022) found that AI hiring does not mitigate or exacerbate ethical concerns, but reconfigures the understanding of moral values, such as fairness, over time. These empirical studies on AI ethics in recruitment revealed that ethical concepts, such as bias, fairness, and objectivity, are not fixed or stable, but actively enacted by different stakeholders in this field. Studying AI bias thus requires a bottom-up approach that explore the material practices of AI developers, HR practitioners, as well as employees and job seekers, to gain a comprehensive understanding on the making and configuration of AI ethics (Seaver, 2021). Work package 4 in the BIAS project has followed a similar thread, conducting interviews and fieldwork with different stakeholders in the field of AI recruitment.

4 Stage 1 of the qualitative work SSH work

4.1 Introduction to Stage 1

The first half of the qualitative data gathering occurred mainly in 2024 and has initially been reported in D4.1. Fieldwork was split in two stages following suggestions by project reviewers during the first Periodic Review (as described in section 4.6 below). Stage 1 primarily consisted of interviews with different stakeholders, as summarized in Table 1, whereas Stage 2 consisted of country-specific case studies based on themes identified through coding and analysis of Stage 1 data (see Chapter 6 for full discussion of this analysis process). These case studies were investigated through longer-term observations with companies. The following sections describe Stage 1 work done and findings in the selected countries that were used to develop Stage 2 case studies.

Stage 1 data collection aimed to understand the extent to which AI was used for recruitment and management purposes and to contextualize the occurrence of bias through these organizational practices and through the development process of AI tools. It sought to explore professional expertise and the lived experience of employees/workers where AI is used for recruitment and/or management and highlight the impact and/or possible impact of AI. It also explored AI ethics, legislation, worker rights, diversity, equity and inclusion practices as well as mitigation strategies for bias and other impacts of AI in relation to health and wellbeing. To map out a more holistic view of the phenomenon, it drew on the expertise and experience of AI and HR experts and civil society representatives (trade/labour unions and NGOs).

Table 1: Total number of interviewees from Stage 1

Country	AI developers	HRM & Employers	Employees & workers' representatives	Total
Italy	1	17	5	23
Norway	14	18	5	37
Iceland	11	7	7	25
Türkiye	0	11	11	21
Total	26	58	42	125

4.2 Stage 1 data collection in Italy

Stage 1 fieldwork in Italy consisted of 17 individual or group interviews with a total of 23 different stakeholders: 13 interviews with HR practitioners and consultants, 3 interviews with workers' representatives, and 1 interview with an AI developer. All interviews were conducted in Italian. Of the 13 HR interviewed 9 of them worked as external HR consultants, recruiters, or headhunters with clients from different sectors, while the four companies interviewed were: one telecommunications company, two manufacturing companies, and one company working in the finance sector. The interviews lasted between 40 minutes and 1 hour and 15 minutes. 9 interviews were conducted online, and 8 interviews were conducted in person. Interviews with the HR practitioners and recruiters focused on the steps of a typical recruitment process and understanding of fairness when not using AI. The interviews also addressed their use or expected use of AI, understanding of AI bias and fairness, perceptions and expectations about the technology. Interviews with workers' representatives focused on the general situation of bias and discrimination in the workplace in Italy and job seekers and employees' potential experiences of discrimination and what impact AI could have on these issues in the context of recruitment.

4.2.1 Stage 1 findings from Italy

The Italian job market has specific characteristics that create differences in the recruitment process depending on the open position. For low-skilled jobs, recruiters¹ mentioned job seekers' tendency to send their CV regardless of their fit for the position. This means that recruiters receive a large number of CVs, many of which can be easily excluded from the search as they immediately emerge as unsuitable for the position. On the other hand, for high-skilled jobs, and especially jobs that require specific technical skills, Italian recruiters are faced with a talent shortage that requires them to do direct headhunting, usually on LinkedIn. In these cases, potential candidates first receive a phone call from the recruiter, which is used to assess mutual interest and "key requirements". Some of the mentioned key requirements are location or availability to move and expected salary level. Once this step has been passed, the short-listed candidates, both for low-skilled and high-skilled jobs, are invited for an interview. The interview process is often in two or more stages, with a first interview with the recruiter, a second with the hiring manager,² and sometimes a third with the company managers. Ultimately, the hiring manager and company manager are the ones with decision making power, and the HR acts as a counselor.

Considering bias and fairness in the general HR hiring process, Italian companies and recruiters do not have a common standard to refer to beyond the legal requirement to include in job descriptions a mention that all candidates are welcome regardless of gender, race, or religion. This was often mentioned, together with the requirement to hire protected categories (individuals with disabilities, medical pathologies, or other forms of psychophysical invalidity) when a certain number of employees is reached. When asked about the specific fairness measures adopted during recruitment, one company showed a particular awareness, as they both anonymized CVs and conducted panel interviews, upholding the idea that including multiple perspectives makes the process less biased. Others, however, usually did not have specific internal policies to follow and referred to their general sensitivity and awareness of their own biases.

Gender bias came up in all interviews and many companies are working towards reducing gender inequalities in their organizations. The Italian government introduced in 2023 the possibility to obtain the "Gender Certification" upon assessment of the situation of gender equality in the company, which leads to fiscal benefits. This "Gender certification" has been mentioned by several HR practitioners as an example of their engagement in achieving gender equality. However, this certification still presents many flaws. Workers' representatives, in fact, felt that Italian companies still have a long way to go before reaching gender equality, and maternity leave is still a major cause of discrimination against women in hiring processes.

Racial bias only rarely came up. In one instance, a company whose workforce is mostly of non-Italian origin elaborated on this in more detail, mentioning, however, how knowledge of the Italian language is a fundamental requirement and other considerations they must make based on a candidate's nationality. Otherwise, racial bias was not mentioned in the interviews.

¹ In this context, recruiter is understood as both the internal HR practitioners in charge of searching for the new employee to be hired as well as external recruiters that may be hired by the company.

² Hiring managers, as opposed to recruiters, are those operational managers who need the new employees to be hired to work in their team and who are involved in some stages of the recruitment process.

Considerations about age were often mentioned in the interviews. These sometimes revealed a lack of awareness regarding age bias. Italian companies retain strict hierarchical structures and, thus, candidates who are younger than the expected age might not be considered for a position, but the same applies to candidates who are considered too old and experienced for an advertised job position.

Out of the 13 HR practitioners (representing 12 different companies) interviewed during Stage 1, 9 reported using AI for some part of their job. The applications mentioned were aimed at:

- Screening and ranking CVs
- Drafting job descriptions
- Analyzing employees' performance data
- Using AI-powered avatars for training
- General use of generative AI for text writing and brainstorming.

Considering the differences in recruitment process mentioned before, recruiters expected AI to help them in screening and ranking of CVs in cases in which they received a high number, but did not think this help was needed for the more high-level jobs with just a few candidates. It must be noted, however, that currently the screening of CVs is done by junior employees, which are the ones with more direct experience of AI use. The use of AI was always motivated by a desire to increase efficiency and gain time. HR practitioners perceived AI as an assistant, a support to their work, taking care of administrative or routine tasks that they did not enjoy doing. Within the recruitment process, however, recruiters were usually resistant to the idea of using AI for interviews, as they believed that meeting the candidates in person was fundamental for evaluating them beyond their hard skills. They also resisted the idea of using AI for the decision-making process which should always be left to people, according to the interviewees.

Lastly, when asked to reflect on AI bias, interviewees were well aware of the risks of using historical data to train AI models and always avoided doing so. However, if the AI models were properly trained, there was ambiguity as to whether AI was viewed as more or less biased than people. On one hand, HR practitioners thought AI makes decisions based on data, objective information, and without being influenced by personal judgement. Thus, it can mitigate human bias and lead to fairer recruitment. This was particularly stressed by workers' representatives, who tended to see AI as an opportunity for making hiring fairer. On the other hand, AI bias can happen without recruiters knowing, due to the black-box effect, and, even if unbiased, basing a hiring decision only on data is not necessarily perceived as a fairer decision. Recruiters agreed that the fact that AI cannot understand context and specific situations makes it more biased. The recruiters' expertise and knowledge, under this perspective, was not a negative factor but a positive one that could lead to a better hiring decision. HR practitioners, thus, believed to be less biased than AI and wished to maintain as much control over the process as possible.

From the Italian Stage 1 several codes related to the HR expertise and HR expectations about AI have been identified. Firstly, codes related to the concept of "gut feeling", human-touch, human component, contextual knowledge or similar ideas were very common, both within the interviews with HR practitioners, which mentioned them in a positive way, and workers' representatives, which mentioned them as a source of bias. These were usually mentioned in connection with mature experience and long-standing knowledge of the field which suggests a potential difference between junior and senior recruiters. Secondly, codes related to expectations about AI were very prominent. For example, seeing AI as an assistant, fearing job loss, expecting a change in skills, balancing human-AI collaboration

and other visions for the future use of AI in HR emerged. This seemed to influence interviewees' use of AI and trust in the technology regarding issues of bias and fairness.

4.3 Stage 1 data collection in Norway

During the Stage 1 fieldwork, 37 interviews with different stakeholders were conducted: 14 interviews with participants working in developer companies, 18 interviews with HR practitioners, and 5 interviews with foreign employees/job seekers in Norway. Half of the interviews were conducted in person, half were online. Two of the interviews were group interviews consisting of different stakeholders.

4.3.1 Stage 1 findings from Norway

The application of AI in hiring and recruitment remains an emerging topic in the Norwegian context. Among the developers and HR technology vendors interviewed, all were familiar with AI at a general level, but only about one-third had integrated AI into their products. This can be seen as a consequence of Norway's economic fabric which is mostly consisting of SMEs with low-volume hiring that do not feel a need to use AI in their HR processes. According to Statistics Norway (SSB) in 2023, over 99% of all businesses in Norway are classified as SMEs, with fewer than 250 employees. These enterprises are vital for employment, as they account for approximately 66% of private sector jobs and contribute significantly to economic value creations. SMEs in Norway also span across various sectors, including technology, services, maritime industries, and renewable energy. For SMEs, hiring is a small-scale HRM practice and usually conducted by manual work from HR recruiters.

Some organizations interviewed that had not yet adopted AI expressed interest in exploring its potential, while others voiced concerns about ethical implications and doubts about its actual effectiveness. A similar pattern was observed among HR practitioners: although most had a general understanding of AI—primarily through media exposure—only a third had actively used AI tools in their work. All HR professionals expressed a positive attitude toward the future use of AI in recruitment, but many emphasized that such adoption would require approval from their organizations. Norway follows both EU regulations on technical implementation but also has separate non-EU legislations that can make implementation difficult. For instance, the Norwegian Data Protection Authority has issued guidelines emphasizing that employers must ensure compliance with the Norwegian Personal Data Act and the Working Environment Act when implementing AI tools in the workplace. Also, the Norwegian Labour Inspection Authority has implemented stricter interpretations of employee data protection under the Working Environment Act, which can complicate the deployment of AI-driven recruitment tools that rely on algorithmic profiling.

No employees or job seekers reported having used AI during their job search process, nor were they aware of whether AI had been used to evaluate their applications. For most, AI in the labor market felt distant and disconnected from their immediate experiences, particularly as many had secured their current roles within recent years. The values of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) emerged as important themes among both developers and HR practitioners. Many of the digital tools developed in the Norwegian context aimed to support fairer and more objective hiring processes. This correlates with a historically high uptake of gender equality policies in Norway. While developers held varied perspectives on whether AI could promote social good—and interpreted “fairness” differently—they consistently prioritized DEI considerations in the design of their tools. HR practitioners also emphasized DEI as central to their professional responsibilities, viewing it not only as a legal obligation but as a core ethical value. Many positioned themselves as

experts and defenders of DEI within their organizations, actively challenging other decision-makers and guiding colleagues to align with inclusive hiring practices.

Finally, among the employee and job seeker participants, all of whom were foreigners, “cultural barriers” were a recurring theme when discussing job-seeking and work experiences in Norway. Norwegian language proficiency was described as a “thick” requirement—not only involving the ability to speak the language, but also to understand and adapt to local norms, workplace habits, and communication styles. Bias and discrimination were often subtle rather than explicit: while participants rarely experienced overt rejection based on their backgrounds, they consistently felt that finding a job was more difficult compared to their Norwegian counterparts, even when holding equal or superior qualifications. In sum, the interviews conducted in Stage 1 offered a snapshot of the current state of AI adoption in Norway’s labor market. While AI is gradually making its way into hiring and recruitment, concerns about bias remain largely unspoken, operating beneath the surface of everyday practice. Codes identified in this stage deal with implicit and explicit understandings of bias and fairness, with and without AI, and AI practices in the workplace.

4.4 Stage 1 data collection in Iceland

Stage 1 fieldwork in Iceland began in December 2023 and lasted until March 2024, with one final interview in June 2024 due to one participant’s unavailability. Fieldwork involving 25 interviews across 13 organizations.³ 22 interviews were conducted in English, and three primarily in English with Icelandic used when necessary. These organizations spanned food processing companies, recruiting and talent management organizations, diversity-oriented tech companies and NGOs, Trade/labor unions, universities, and research institutions, as well as banks and airlines. 19 of the interviews were conducted in person and 6 interviews were done via MS Teams. The interviewees comprised 7 HR experts, 11 AI experts and 7 representatives of civil society organizations (CSO). Of the 25 interviews, 13 interviews were conducted across 3 of the 13 organizations. This was to explore more in-depth three distinct areas: the manufacturing of AI automated fish processing and monitoring systems (prior to visiting the fish factories); bias free recruiting systems; the role of trade/labor Unions. Interviews in these three organizations were focused to address these specific areas as explained below. More generally, however, all interviews with AI experts focused on the evolution and development of AI tools and how bias can occur in this process, training data, parameter setting, developer autonomy, limitations of AI, DEI, AI fairness, bias and mitigation strategies, AI ethics and ethical considerations during the development phase. All HR expert interviews focused on the recruitment process and management process, how bias could occur as well as be mitigated. Interviews with all the CSO representatives focused on their perception of the use of AI in HRM practices. Issues of bias and fairness in the

³ Icelandic fieldwork progressed more quickly than for other countries, and the decision to do preliminary interviews followed by more in-depth case studies was made prior to the decision to have a formal Stage 1 and Stage 2 division for all BIAS fieldwork. Thus, in D4.1, interviews already conducted at a fish factory (a site for in depth case studies), was reported as part of Stage 1 fieldwork. Thus, in D4.1, 44 participants were recorded for Stage 1. However, for this report D4.2 and, after a thorough discussion and recommendations from the project advisory board, we have only classified interviews conducted prior to the study of the fish factories as Stage 1 (25 interviews) while classifying the more in-depth case study of fish factories as stage 2. Since in the D4.1 report an additional fish factory was studied (totaling 25 interviews). Through this, we establish coherence with the other countries studied under work package 4 in how we divide the data collection into Stages 1 and 2.

workplace, bias mitigation and the role of civil society organizations in the strife towards fair and responsible AI usage. All participants were asked about general workplace bias and fairness, ethics, the role of different stakeholders, workers' rights, general impact and impact on employees' wellbeing.

4.4.1 Organizational study one: Manufacturing of AI automated fish processing and monitoring systems

In preparation for the case study to be conducted within Icelandic fish factories, a preliminary study was carried out with nine participants from a company specializing in food processing and the development of AI-automated fish processing and monitoring systems used in the fishing industry. While AI for recruitment is rarely applied in the Icelandic context due to the fact that most organizations in Iceland are SMEs, the use of AI for management—particularly within the fisheries sector—is more prevalent. The study involved a full day visit to the company, which included direct observation of organizational processes, as well as interviews with one HR expert and seven AI experts. The visit began with a guided 30-minute tour of the facility. The HR expert provided an overview of the company's operations and explained their motivations for developing AI-based tools for fish processing. During the tour, we observed the production of hardware components and were introduced to a sample of the AI-powered processing system.

Following the tour, interviews were conducted with the HR representative and the AI developers responsible for the software behind the automated systems. Each interview lasted between 40 minutes and 75 minutes. The discussions focused on the organization's specific operations, the AI tool, and general perspectives on the use of AI in human resource management (HRM), aligning with the broader objectives of BIAS. Although the organization did not particularly use AI in its recruitment practices (except for LinkedIn), the HR manager expressed interest in exploring such technologies in the future. Currently, the company utilizes third-party platforms—such as LinkedIn—to search candidate profiles. During the HR interview, we explored the company's recruitment and employee management processes, with particular attention to how bias might occur and be addressed. The discussion also covered the potential impact of AI tools on employee wellbeing, and how the organization approaches diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI), particularly in relation to fairness and bias mitigation. The underlying assumption is that organizations already engaged in DEI practices may be more likely to consider these factors when adopting AI in future HRM applications.

The HR manager noted that despite efforts to promote gender equality, there remains a significant gender imbalance in the technology and manufacturing field, largely due to a lack of female specialists in this area of work. Nonetheless, as a multinational company, the Icelandic branch has made progress, with women accounting for 25% of new hires—above the company's global average of 18%. The interviews with AI experts focused on the development of the AI-automated fish processing and monitoring system, as well as broader topics such as the design of AI tools for recruitment, the risks and mitigation of bias, AI ethics, and the responsibilities of developers in ensuring ethical outcomes. One additional HR interview was conducted via Microsoft Teams in late March, prior to the fieldwork in fish factories, to further understand the AI systems in use and to inform about the next stage of data collection. The aim was to get further information on technology utilized in fish processing that involves AI, and to understand how AI technology functions in part for monitoring and performance evaluation of employees. Subsequently, we decided which fish processing plants would be selected for case studies. One of the plants chosen was temporally closed before it could be visited, due to a volcanic eruption, but may be included at a later stage in our research if the occasion arrives.

4.4.2 Organizational study two: Bias free recruiting systems

At the time of fieldwork, this recruitment and talent-based organization was developing a recruitment tool aimed at mitigating bias in the recruitment process for fairer hiring processes. They had made some agreements with organizations in Iceland who were interested in purchasing this tool for recruitment once it was out. Two interviews were conducted with key members of the recruitment organization. The first interview was held in February 2024 with the AI expert in charge of designing this AI based tool and another in June 2024 with a Co-founder who also serves as an HR lead; this interview had initially been scheduled for February but was postponed due to personal reasons of the interviewee. The purpose of these interviews was to gain insight into how the recruitment tool was being developed, how it aimed to operationalize principles of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI), and how it was expected to function in practice. During the interview with the AI expert, the tool's development process was explained, including the anticipated user experience for job applicants. Topics discussed included the selection and use of training data, parameter settings, the extent of developer autonomy, strategies for bias detection and mitigation, as well as the degree of customization the tool would allow for client organizations. Additional questions addressed broader themes related to AI in recruitment, aligning with the study's overall focus. In the HR interview, the organization's broader vision was explored, particularly its commitment to reducing bias in recruitment processes. The current practices in recruiting on behalf of client companies were also discussed and how the new tool would be integrated into these services. The conversation addressed anticipated challenges, strategies for implementation, and best practices for ensuring fairness in hiring. Finally, the way DEI values were embedded into both the organization's mission and the development of the tool was examined, along with reflections on the broader role of AI in transforming recruitment practices.

4.4.3 Organizational study three: The role of trade/labor Unions

Worker representative organizations, such as trade and labor unions, occupy a critical position in ongoing discussions about the use of AI in the workplace, particularly given the diverse and potentially uneven impacts of these technologies on workers. In this organization, two interviews were conducted: one with the head of the union department and another with a unionized worker. The interviews explored a range of themes, including perceptions of AI use in recruitment and management, concerns about algorithmic bias and fairness in both hiring and workplace decision-making, and the nature of workers' complaints related to digital management systems. Attention was also given to the impact of AI technologies on employee well-being and workers' rights and the broader role of trade unions in advocating for fair and transparent HRM practices in the context of technological change. Additionally, the conversations surfaced broader concerns related to gender inequalities, labor exploitation, and the treatment of immigrant workers in Iceland. These issues highlighted the intersection between AI in HRM and existing social hierarchies, emphasizing the importance of organizational and societal accountability as digital technologies become increasingly embedded in the labor process.

4.4.4 Stage 1 findings from Iceland

All Stage 1 interviews complement each other when examining each participant group individually as well as collectively, given their specific areas of focus. This allows for an efficient and clear analysis of both group-specific and cross-group data. Findings indicate that although AI is not widely used for recruitment in Iceland, it is employed in various management processes to optimize workflows—such as managing work and personal schedules, scheduling meetings, keeping track of and communicating with co-workers in

different locations (both within and outside Iceland), assisting with information sourcing, writing, and performing spell checks. Some of the HR experts used third party HR hiring platforms. Although it is unknown whether these platforms use AI it is evident that they employ some form of algorithm to search for and screen candidates. Interview data from AI developers revealed that bias can occur during the development phase, particularly resulting from the training data used and the parameters set for the algorithm. Training data sourced from the internet or based on historical company data was considered likely to introduce bias if it overrepresents or underrepresents certain groups, or if the language contained in the data reflected biased views. This may cause the AI to replicate and even amplify such biases. The interviewees believed developers' unconscious biases might also influence data selection and parameter setting, especially given that developers often have a high degree of autonomy in these decisions. A limited understanding of bias-related issues could, therefore, result in insufficient consideration for bias mitigation during the development process.

AI experts emphasized that developers of AI tools for recruitment and management hold ethical responsibilities to ensure fair use of data, transparency in how their systems operate, and clear communication of system limitations. They noted that many AI tools marketed to organizations are often exaggerated in terms of their capabilities. The term “snake oil” was commonly used by experts to describe this phenomenon. Two forms of bias were identified as particularly problematic in recruitment: confirmation bias—shaped by stereotypes—and affinity bias—driven by the tendency to favor candidates similar to oneself. HR experts noted that bias could occur at multiple stages of the recruitment process, including job advertisement, screening, assessment, interviews, and selection. This included issues such as gendered language in job postings, exclusionary algorithm parameters during candidate searches, biased assessment tools, and video interviews using AI.

It was noted across stakeholders that HR practitioners and companies often viewed AI tools as infallible and place excessive trust in them, making them less likely to question or consider potential biases. All participants agreed that AI was best used to support, rather than monitor or control, employees as its use could have diverse effects on health, well-being, safety, and job security. These included increased stress and anxiety, loss of autonomy, reduced trust, fear of data breaches, and broader ethical concerns. Regarding workers' rights, participants expressed concern that AI-based monitoring violates privacy. Workers were not always aware they were being monitored by AI, and participants argued that employees had the right to be informed and to opt out of such monitoring.

Many civil society organization (CSO) representatives emphasized that bias mitigation should be embedded in the organizational culture and considered throughout all phases of recruitment and management. Trade unions, they argued, could play an important role by advocating for the proper implementation of legislation to protect workers' rights. Other suggested mitigation strategies included raising awareness and providing training on bias and rights for AI developers, HR professionals, and employees. Emphasis was placed on the importance of training data screening, the use of supplementary datasets, integrating user feedback during AI development, ensuring diversity within developer and recruitment teams, anonymizing CVs, preparing both companies and employees before AI adoption, setting diversity quotas, fostering inclusive work environments, ensuring transparency and human oversight, and establishing internal or third-party bias audit systems for AI tools.

4.5 Stage 1 in the Netherlands

The Netherlands is a priority country for the BIAS project and subject to Stage 2 fieldwork. With the restructuring requested from evaluators into two stages of data collection, it was

decided in discussion with the project PO that the Netherlands' fieldwork could go directly into stage 2 data collection (and not have the initial interview stage that evaluators wanted less off). Details of Dutch Stage 2 fieldwork is provided in Section 5.7

4.6 Stage 1 in Türkiye

Türkiye was initially planned as a priority country for the BIAS project, but due to a shift in the research group with the departure of the Turkish data collector and insufficient data it was decided in discussion with the PO to shift the project focus more on the other four countries (which produced positive results) and removing Türkiye from Stage 2 fieldwork. The following summary, building on D4.1, describes the Stage 1 Turkish fieldwork⁴. 21 interviews with HR officers and employees were conducted in Türkiye in Turkish, as well as a fieldwork observation of a hiring process where AI was used.

Preliminary analysis of the collected data highlighted university biases, sex-based biases, biases related to gender segregation across professions, gender expression and identity biases, and regional biases as influential in hiring decisions. The primary focus in the fieldwork and interviews was to explore how fairness was conceptualized and how the study participants perceived the role of AI. The sample of interviewees predominantly represented a group already invested in or enthusiastic about AI integration, which may have influenced the generally positive attitudes observed towards the use of AI in hiring. Preliminary findings regarding these questions show that the notion of fairness in recruitment processes was predominantly interpreted by the interviewed HR officers and employers as "equal treatment." This perspective highlighted an approach where all candidates are provided with the same opportunities, resources, and evaluation criteria during the recruitment process. The emphasis on equal treatment reflects a commitment to creating a level playing field, ensuring that no individual is disadvantaged based on subjective or irrelevant factors. Neither the interviewed employees nor the HR officers or employers considered the concept of equity as an alternative or complementary approach to fairness. While equity focuses on addressing individual differences and providing tailored support to candidates who might face unique challenges, this nuanced view seemed to be overshadowed by the more straightforward principle of equal treatment. This lack of engagement with equity suggests a gap in how fairness is conceptualized and applied in recruitment practices according to the Turkish data collected.

This observation raises critical questions about whether the pursuit of equal treatment alone is sufficient to achieve true fairness in diverse and dynamic workplaces. In certain scenarios, equal treatment may inadvertently perpetuate existing inequalities, as it does not account for varying levels of access, privilege, or barriers faced by candidates from underrepresented or marginalized backgrounds. Consequently, a deeper exploration of how equity could complement or enhance fairness in recruitment may provide a more robust and inclusive framework. Most of the interviewees expressed a generally positive outlook on the integration of AI into recruitment processes, particularly in its potential to mitigate subjective biases. AI systems were widely perceived as "neutral" and "objective," qualities that were seen as valuable contributions to a company's commitment to fairness, often understood as providing equal treatment to all candidates. This belief underscores the

⁴ The summary presented in this report is a shortened version of a full fieldwork report authored by Öznur Karakaş.

expectation that AI can help standardize recruitment practices by eliminating the personal preferences or unconscious biases of individual decision-makers.

However, interviewees also acknowledged the limitations of AI in achieving this ideal. While they recognized that AI systems could introduce biases, these were largely attributed to flaws introduced by human programmers and constraints inherent in the technological design and not affordances of AI. For example, biases in training data or algorithmic decision-making processes were seen as reflecting the biases present in the humans who develop and train these systems. An interviewee called it as follows; “those who have control of the ‘if’s”, also control the system.”

Despite their optimism about AI's potential, HR officers and employers emphasized the continued importance of a "human touch" in recruitment processes. While AI can assist by screening applications, analyzing data, or even identifying patterns that humans might overlook, there was a shared belief that humans should ultimately make the final decisions. Furthermore, interviewees highlighted the need for ethical oversight and continuous monitoring of AI tools to ensure that their implementation aligned with a company's values and fairness objectives. They suggested that AI integration should not replace human involvement but rather complement it by enhancing efficiency and objectivity while leaving room for human intuition and discretion in complex or ambiguous situations.

While AI integration in recruitment was seen as a promising step toward reducing subjective biases and promoting fairness, the interviewees advocated for a balanced approach. They envisioned a recruitment process where AI and human decision-making coexisted, leveraging the strengths of both to create a more effective system. This perspective reinforces the idea that technology should serve as a tool to support—not replace—human judgment in the pursuit of fair and inclusive recruitment practices. Another key observation during the fieldwork was the significant reliance on third-party vendor companies to handle AI-based recruitment processes. This delegation underscored a common approach where organizations outsource the technical complexities and infrastructure required for AI integration to external providers. The dependence on third-party vendors may reflect the challenges HR departments face in building in-house AI capabilities, particularly for organizations with limited resources or technical expertise. However, this reliance introduced additional considerations, such as ensuring that external systems align with the company's values, data privacy policies, and broader fairness objectives.

4.7 Shared findings on similarities and differences in stage 1 countries

The first stage of fieldwork was coded separately, and then combined into a stage 1 codebook,⁵ consisting of 366 codes: 83 from the Italian interviews, 173 from the Norwegian interviews, and 80 from the Icelandic interviews.⁶ The differences in codes numbers reflect differences in coding styles, however, the content of the codes was very similar. From these initial codes, several common themes were identified: recruitment process, job seeking process, understandings of fairness and bias, diversity and DEI, AI use, understandings of

⁵ The process of developing this codebook, its theoretical basis, and details concerning analysis, including how this analysis informed Stage 2 fieldwork, are provided in Chapter 6: Analytical Framework of this deliverable

⁶ Due to data insufficiency in Türkiye and no data from stage 1 part from the Netherlands, the remainder of the report and analysis focuses on Italy, Norway and the Netherlands.

AI fairness and bias, perceptions and expectations about AI. Based on these stage 1 codes, we present a comparison between the three countries.

Across the three countries, the recruitment process appears very similar. The most significant differences are usually based on the sector and position being hired for rather than the country. Recruitment usually begins with drafting a job description starting from an open position, which is then advertised. LinkedIn is mentioned by interviewees in all three countries; however, they also mention other country-specific platforms. For example, Icelandic recruiters mention Alfred, Gera, Tvinna, and Kjarni, Norwegian recruiters mention Finn and Jobbnorge, and Italian recruiters mention Infojobs, Indeed and Monster. These external platforms have been flagged for follow up in Stage 2 analysis.

After advertisement, recruiters often contact the candidates for a pre-selection phase by either phone or email in which they make sure the candidate is still interested in the position and schedule an interview. The number and format of the interview varies depending on the organization and position. At least one interview always takes place, this can be followed by one or two more interviews or by assessment tests. These interviews, regardless of their number, usually include the recruiter or HR manager and the hiring manager, while also sometimes including the organization's leader. While in Norway and Iceland it is the norm to provide feedback to all applicants once the selection process is closed, in Italy this is not an obligation and is often not done.

Regarding the use of AI for recruitment, there are some differences between countries. In Italy, HR practitioners report an increasing number of AI applications for recruitment on the market and an increasing use of these applications especially for CV screening. In Iceland, organizations focus more on the use of AI for employee management or administrative tasks, for example, performance evaluation, scheduling meetings, or connecting colleagues across offices. The latter use is particularly interesting in Iceland as employees often need to connect with offices across and outside of Iceland. In Norway AI is not yet widely diffused even if some applications are emerging, especially for drafting job descriptions or brainstorming interview questions. The differences here can also be tied to the population of the countries and relatively, the number of speakers of the language.

Using AI for interviewing is not common in any of the three countries and is often frowned upon by HR practitioners who believe that human contact is still fundamental during the interview process. The use of AI for training and onboarding, on the other hand, seems to be gaining popularity in all three countries, for example, with AI-powered tools for training. Overall, interviewees across countries agree that AI should be an assistant in the recruitment process and not replace recruiters entirely.

The way in which bias emerges during the recruitment process varies from country to country depending on the country's demographics and job market. In Iceland and in Norway, bias against foreign names and immigrant background is often mentioned by participants, and age bias is also a popular topic discussed by HR practitioners. Gender bias is seldomly mentioned in these countries compared with Italy, although it is used mostly as hypothetical examples in Iceland when discussing bias. Bias based on disability, and social status is also mentioned in Iceland. In Italy, gender bias is the main focus also due to the gender certification process many companies are going through, while race bias was severely overlooked. Age also emerged as an important cause of bias in Italy depending on the advertised position. All these diversity criteria have been flagged as important cornerstones for the Stage 2 studies and further mapping.

Some power dynamics within the recruitment process were shared by the three countries. Bias is linked to organizational cultures that apply affinity bias to look for people who are

already comparable with the company's current employees and/or recruiters. Foreign workers in Norway perceived this as a "cultural barrier" with culture being used as an implicit way to discriminate non-Norwegian applicants. Language is also an important matter in all three countries where the local language is seen as an important requirement for hiring people. Lastly, interviewees in all three countries mentioned similar obstacles when it comes to fair recruitment related to networking, or internal hiring. In Norway, foreign job seekers reported that knowing people and networking is fundamental for finding a job in Norway. In Iceland and Italy, a similar tendency emerged, and companies often recruit internally or through their employees before advertising externally. This can create bias in the advertising phase of recruitment as the job ad only reaches certain people and affinity bias is further reinforced.

Data from Stage 1 interviews showed that countries approached the relationship between AI and DEI differently. In Norway AI is usually linked to DEI initiatives and expected to improve diversity and inclusion in the workplace through unbiased recruitment. The companies selling AI tools in Norway stress this view and market their tools as instruments to improve DEI in companies. Differently, in Italy AI adoption is driven by a wish for increased efficiency and faster recruitment and the link between AI and DEI did not emerge as strongly as in Norway. In Iceland AI was seen as both the problem and the solution, as it could lead to unfair recruitment and worker management but could also be used to improve hiring and workplace fairness, work processes, efficiency, and productivity. Despite these differences, across countries some interviewees recognized that AI could lead to neutral hiring decisions but usually the value of AI was seen in its potential for increased productivity. This could reflect the different role that HR was expected to play amongst all countries. In Norway, the HR department within a company often was perceived having the role of a "friend" to the employees and furthering their interests with the company. On the other hand, in Italy, internal HR departments are usually in a difficult position as intermediaries between management and employees but often linked more closely to company interests rather than employees' (However, these interviewees indicated that in recent years this may have subtly changed.) In Iceland, although HR experts did not explicitly state their roles, it was inferred from their views on workplace bias and fairness and in the case of recruitment organizations that their consideration was for the interest of both applicants/employees and companies as they took on the roles of both 'friend' and intermediary.

Popular discourses about AI in the workplace either replacing or supporting people are mentioned by interviewees in all three countries. Although individuals in each country thought of this differently, similar cross-country narratives emerged from the data. Fear of replacement has been mentioned by stakeholders in all three countries. In Italy, this is often presented as a fear among the "general public" but minimized by those HR practitioners who have had an opportunity to use AI in their job. In Iceland it was interesting to note that AI developers were more concerned about AI replacing the jobs of HR experts than HR experts themselves. These, on the other hand, in all three countries, adopted different stances regarding the future of AI for their profession, seeing it as an inevitable process that will lead to changes in skills needed in the workplace, but they saw AI as an assistive tool rather than a replacement. HR experts strongly believed that there are parts of the HRM processes that could only be conducted by human beings and a lot more is needed for AI to reach that point since it had no emotions or broad oversight into the personal lives of employees. Consequently, the hope was for AI to take over routine or boring administrative tasks and leave HR practitioners more time for the creative and more meaningful parts of their job. Although embracing this advanced technology, interviewees emphasized that

humans should always be involved in all activities, overseeing AI, and in charge of the final decision making. We will continue to explore this theme in Stage 2 of the fieldwork as well.

These findings from Stage 1 have been important in shaping Stage 2 of the fieldwork which we describe in the following section. Limitations and adaptations for Stage 1 have been thoroughly addressed D4.1, where the major limitation on scope of fieldwork has been addressed in the splitting of the fieldwork into the two respective stages. We further describe methodological limitations for each country under the Stage 2 descriptions for each country for further specificity.

4.8 Transitioning from stage 1 to stage 2 data collection

Following the completion of Stage 1 fieldwork, we decided upon comments from the project evaluators to split the fieldwork into distinct stages, whereas Stage 1 consisted of primarily interviews with some observations and visits to the field as well as some group interviews that were treated like a first informative half of the fieldwork. This “first stage” was then used to build knowledge for the second more on-site focused qualitative data collection. This investigation was built around specific cases that emerged from Stage 1 data. This “Stage 2” of the fieldwork could then prioritize more in-depth case studies, as requested from the evaluators. As mentioned, the first stage of the fieldwork generated 366 different codes across Italy, Norway and Iceland. From these, we identified shared common *themes*. The most important themes are:

- Recruitment process
- Job seeking process
- Understandings of fairness and bias
- Diversity and DEI
- AI use
- Understandings of fairness and bias specifically related to AI
- Perceptions and expectations about AI.

From these themes, we decided to focus on specific themes and methods for county-specific case studies, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Themes and methods for Stage 2

Country	Theme	Method
Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HR expertise • HR junior / senior differences • Expectations about AI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews with HR practitioners • Observations with recruiters • Observation of a university level HR course • Focus groups with HR practitioners and students • Document analysis
Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI tool developed for hiring and recruitment • AI usage among HR recruiters • The cultural barrier faced by job seekers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews with HR recruiters/AI developers/job seekers • Observation at recruitment agency/development company • Shadow job seekers for 1-2 days to study their daily practices
Iceland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI based performance monitoring and evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews with HR management • Interviews with employees • Observations in fish factories

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact on the health and wellbeing of workers • Workers' rights safety and security • Perceptions of bias and/or fairness in the workplace and towards AI • The recruitment experience • Organizational and employee preparedness for AI 	
The Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The job seeker experience • AI tool development • AI-based recruitment and management processes: AI/algorithm-based assessment tools • AI ethics, bias and mitigation • The perception and role of civil societies, legislation and workers' rights 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interview with AI experts/developers • Interview with HR practitioners • Interview with representatives of civil society organizations • Testing assessment tool and reviewing internal documents/data

5 Stage 2 of the qualitative SSH work

Stage 2 started in spring 2024. When transitioning to the second stage of the fieldwork, several internal workshops were held to determine the best path forward for transiting from more analytical interview focused work into thicker case studies. We also decided to base Stage 2 work on developing case studies based on important themes and preliminary findings found in stage 1. These themes are listed below:

Key themes explored in Italy

- The role of HR expertise in recruitment processes linked to the concept of “gut feeling” and if and how this should be translated into an AI system
- Differences between junior and senior recruiters, including HR in training, and how their different roles can impact their AI use
- Expectations about the future of AI and how this impact use of AI in HR and HR’s trust in AI

Key themes explored in Norway

- The operationalization of “fairness” concept in AI-based HR tools: how developer interpretate fairness in technical features
- Cultural barriers for foreign job seekers in Norway, including their struggles on job seeking and what biases/discrimination they perceived during the job seeking process
- HR practitioners’ interaction with AI tools, how they use AI to facilitate hiring and recruitment process

Key themes explored in Iceland

- AI for worker management, a concept that has gained publicity and raised great concern at the EU level: the lived experience of workers
- AI based performance monitoring and evaluation of workers with and without the reward for individual bonuses
- Workers’ rights and the impact of AI worker management on the wellbeing and health of workers
- The concept of fairness, safety and security in high tech production environments
- Organizational and employee preparedness
- The recruitment experience

Key themes explored in the Netherlands

As the Netherlands did not have the initial stage 1 interviews, the following themes were discussed to be of extra interest to explore for case studies in the Netherlands:

- Non EU/EEA citizens’ job seeking experience in the Netherlands, with a special focus on Chinese community
- The development of AI tools used in recruitment and management
- AI based recruitment and management: exploring the use of assessment/management tool, fairness, bias and mitigation, AI ethics and legislation
- The perception and role of civil society organizations (e.g. workers unions, rights-based organizations, policy based advisory agencies), legislation and workers’ rights

5.1.1 Overview stage 2 fieldwork

Table 3 provides an overview of Stage 2 fieldwork in each country:

Table 3: Stage 2 fieldwork overview

Country	Stage 2 Fieldwork	Data types	Duration
Italy	10 interviews, 2 focus groups, analysis of 14 articles on AI and HR, 3 observations (4 lectures of HR course, 12 hours of observation for case 1, 1 week of observation for case 2)	Observation Interviews Focus groups Document analysis of articles	3 months of fieldwork in total
Norway	24 individual interviews, 4 weeks of observation in total with fieldwork notes, in addition, MA student theses with qualitative interviews supervised by the Norwegian BIAS team.	Observation Interviews Field journal	3 months of fieldwork in total
Iceland	4 fish factory case studies consisting of 25 interviews and 4 observations	Interviews Observations Field journal	3 months of fieldwork in total
The Netherlands	7 individual interviews, 1 week of observation in total with fieldwork notes, 3 case studies constituting 12 interviews, 1 organizational observation and review of internal documents (published articles, organization’s documents on their work, sample assessment results)	Observation Interviews Field journal	2 months of fieldwork in total

5.2 Stage 2 in Italy

Stage 2 Italian fieldwork consisted of interviews, observations, and focus groups with different stakeholders. 10 individual or group interviews have been conducted: 6 with HR practitioners or recruiters, 3 with university professors in HR, and 1 with a job seeker. These interviews complemented data from Stage 1 by delving deeper into HR practices in AI use and the expertise of HR practitioners in relation to both differences between junior and senior recruiters and common narratives and expectations about the future of AI for HR. Two focus groups were organized, one with HR practitioners, and one with university students from a faculty of psychology. These focus groups were useful for gathering information about the expected future of AI and work from people at different moments of their career.

Considering the aim of Stage 2 being more focused on fieldwork and observations, the beginning of Stage 2 was dedicated to scouting for companies who made explicit use of AI in recruitment. Out of the Stage 1 interviewees, only one company would have been a suitable match for fieldwork for this research, while all other HR practitioners either did not use AI for recruitment or used it in a non-systematic manner (e.g. occasional use of ChatGPT to draft a job description). The most suitable company from Stage 1 is, however, a semi-public company which had a complex and bureaucratic procedure to arrange permission for an external researcher to conduct observations. For that reason, the company had to be excluded from the data collection process. In the end, through LinkedIn and snowball sampling, two companies were found. Thus, Stage 2 fieldwork in Italy was characterized by three periods of observations. One observation of an HR university course within a master's in management and entrepreneurship, which complemented interviews with HR

professors, intended to investigate the professional identity of HR practitioners and how the use of AI is taught and framed in this context. One observation of a recruitment process with a head-hunting company specialized in the tech sector. One week of observation with the HR team of a social cooperative (similar to an NGO) using generative AI to support candidates' evaluation and planning the introduction of further AI-powered tools for recruitment. These two company-based observations are described in more detail below.

Stage 2 in Italy also includes the analysis of 14 magazine articles, 4 from the Italian Association of HR Managers (*Associazione Italiana Direttori del Personale – AIDP*) and 10 from *HR Link*, a well-known Italian HR magazine. These two sources have been selected as they emerged during Stage 1 as important sources of information for HR practitioners. Both sources' websites have been searched for articles published in 2024 mentioning "Artificial Intelligence" or "AI". From these, the ones promoting events have been eliminated, resulting in the 14 selected articles. The analysis of these will be finalized alongside the analysis of all other data material.

All individual's and companies' names are pseudonyms.

5.2.1 Case one: University-level course in HRM

The first observation pertained to a university-level course in Human Resource Management. The course was offered as part of the master's course in Management and Entrepreneurship at an Italian University during the fall semester 2024. The course was structured in two weekly lectures on campus. One four-hour lecture on Mondays focused on theories and notions needed to manage human resources, and one two-hour lecture on Fridays during which an external HR professional was invited to present their experience relating to a particular HR process. It was possible to follow two weeks of the course for a total of 12 hours and four lectures. The classroom was very small, with around seven to ten students attending every lecture with which it was possible to chat before and after the lectures. The information gathered during the course has been complemented by interviews with three HR professors, one of which was involved in the planning of the observed course, and two other professors teaching human resources management in two other universities in the north of Italy. Conversations with these two other professors allowed for the comparison of the observed course with reflections from other contexts.

5.2.2 Case two: Tech Hire

Regular observations have been conducted with Tech Hire, a head-hunting company specializing in the tech sector. Tech Hire is a small and young head-hunting company, with a fixed team of four people: the two co-founders (an HR expert and an IT expert), one recruiter, and one recruiter/sales manager. The company specializes in recruitment in the tech sector and has also leveraged their co-founders' IT expertise to create their own AI-powered platform which supports their recruiters and their clients. To create this platform, they used the GPT-4 AI model. The platform, from the Tech Hire side, provides a CV summary and evaluation for each applicant and the so-called "proxy skills" tool. This is an AI tool where recruiters can input a technical skill (for example, a coding language like Python) and they will be provided with a list of "proxy skills" (equally adequate skills) which can help them expand the pool of candidates. From the client side, the platform can be used to generate job descriptions, explain IT jargon (useful for HR practitioners who might not be tech-savvy but still need to understand a job description), and generate interview questions. Clients also have access to a dashboard visually representing the recruitment process through data. Except for the dashboard, the previously mentioned client-facing

tools are, by Tech Hire's own admission, not very popular among their clients and they suspect they are not used very often.

With Tech Hire, a first individual interview with one of the co-founders was conducted. Then, after having agreed on the participation of the company in the research, an initial visit to their offices took place during which the BIAS project was presented to their team. During this first visit it was possible to already hear the opinions of the other team members about AI use in recruitment and the opportunities and challenges they encountered with their platform. Following this initial visit, a second visit to their offices took place during which the team was interviewed in a group interview and then observed working. After the second visit, however, it was decided that the following observations would be conducted online as the team works remotely four days a week and meets at the office only one day per week. It was also mutually agreed that the research would be following a specific selection process, which was chosen by the company.

For the digital observations which took place after the two on-site visits, it was decided to follow up on a search for a sales manager specialized in cybersecurity. The digital observations were conducted mainly with Alberto, the company's recruiter and responsible for this search, and Federica, one of the co-founders. Alberto and BIAS project researcher met online approximately every other week. During the first meeting Alberto showed the platform in detail and did the screening of two candidates. Then, during the following meetings, he updated the status of the selection process, showed the new applications they had received and screened some candidates. Once they identified three top candidates, it was possible to observe one of the interviews. During the following meetings Alberto updated the status of the selection process, now involving also the client, once the shortlisted candidates had been presented and showed their AI-powered tool for writing candidate's evaluations, and the client-facing tools. The observation with Tech Hire concluded once the selection process for a sales manager specialized in cybersecurity had been closed. Overall, between in-person visits and digital observations, approximately 12 hours of fieldwork with Tech Hire were conducted.

5.2.3 Case three: Social Farm

For the second observation, the HR team of Social Farm was followed for one week. Social Farm is a *cooperativa sociale* (social cooperative) which is an Italian term used to describe companies, similar to NGOs, with the aim of serving society and with a governance model where workers are also shareholders. Social Farm manages several structures and services: for example, day centers for people with varying degrees of disability, domestic assistance for children and adolescents under the care of social services. This wide range of services means that the cooperative also hires a wide range of profiles with varying requirements in terms of qualifications and experience. Some positions are always open due to a lack of workforce, like the social health workers (*operatori socio-sanitari*) needed for the day centers, or the educators for the domestic assistance services. Social Farm's HR department had only been formally established two years prior to the observation and is composed of nine people, three of which are involved in the recruitment processes: the HR director, the recruitment manager, and a junior recruiter. AI is not formally established as a tool for recruitment, however, during the first interview with the cooperative's junior recruiter it emerged that the HR director advised him to use ChatGPT to support him in his job, particularly to fill in candidates' evaluation forms and draft candidates' synthetic evaluations. In addition, the cooperative was, at the time of the visit, undergoing a digitalization process with the aim of introducing a number of digital tools, including a recruitment platform with AI integrations. While this project was planned to take place in

the fall 2024, it was delayed, thus, it was possible to observe a planning meeting during the observation but not see the results of it.

At Social Farm, one week of observations was conducted, spending five working days at their office, mainly following the junior recruiter Lorenzo, who is exclusively in charge of selection and recruitment, but also interacting with the HR director and recruitment manager. During this week, it was possible to observe seven interviews in relation to several open positions for different services and structures, and all the following evaluation forms and synthetic evaluations done by Lorenzo regarding the seven candidates. Six of the seven interviews were first interviews and have been conducted exclusively by Lorenzo, while one was a second interview and was conducted by Lorenzo and the service manager hiring the employee. In addition, it was possible to observe some meetings between Lorenzo and the recruitment manager to discuss the status of open searches, and one planning meeting with the external company in charge of the digitalization project.

5.2.4 Preliminary findings in Italy

Reinforcing what was already found in Stage 1, Stage 2 interviewees and participants engaged with the concept of HR expertise or “gut feeling” especially in relation to interviews. The main limitation of using AI for recruitment was identified in AI’s lack of contextual knowledge. The observations with Tech Hire and Social Farm particularly showed the importance of knowing the context for which you are recruiting, not understood only as company culture, but also the specificity of the profession you are hiring for and the norms and jargon that applicants might take for granted. The observations highlighted the complexity of being a recruiter, which requires very wide and flexible knowledge about each open position. During the search for a sales manager in cybersecurity, for example, Alberto had to ask the Tech Hire’s sales manager for advice and explanation about sales strategies and performance measurements for salespersons. While acquiring this contextual knowledge could be done also with the support of AI, like with Tech Hire’s proxy skills tool, interviewees stressed its intrinsically human component and how acquiring it goes through experience. This further explains how the potential differences between junior and senior HR practitioners could impact AI use in recruitment. The effects of this on the process’ fairness will need further analysis. Some interviewees mentioned how having this experience supports recruiters in making better decisions, while others recognized that junior recruiters with less experience adhere more strictly to procedures and thus might take more objective decisions.

Regarding future expectations for AI in HR, an important topic that emerged during Stage 2 fieldwork and will be further explored as the analysis progresses is the theme of time. AI is expected to increase productivity, which in the context of recruitment means saving time. The usual motivation for introducing AI was to make screening candidates faster, this also translated into allowing HR practitioners to dedicate more time to the tasks that they considered more meaningful. The initial analysis of magazine articles also showed a focus on increased efficiency as a popular narrative. Through the observations, however, a mismatch was identified which will be further explored, as the use of AI on a daily basis was not motivated by a need for more time for the HR practitioners but rather as their cognitive support. For example, Lorenzo would use ChatGPT to write synthetic evaluations when he was very tired, such as at the end of the day just before going home as at that time he felt the need for cognitive support. Similarly, Alberto at Tech Hire screened CVs regardless of the AI evaluation but reverted to the AI summary and evaluation when he needed help in remembering who the candidates were and what he thought about them. While there is surely a component of time saving, there is still ambiguity as to whether the expected effect of AI saving time is actually achieved. In addition, through observing the university HR

course and interviewing HR professors, a tension emerged in the data between the HR identification with employees' wellbeing and their need to show their strategic role in companies. For example, the course stressed the strategic role of HR within a company which would suggest a use of AI for efficiency, while, however, the students mentioned an interest in HR as a way of increasing employees wellbeing which would suggest a use of AI for making work easier.

It is interesting to note that the magazine articles analyzed pose a strong emphasis on the pitfalls of AI use for HRM and issues of bias and workers replacement. These are strongly concerned with the ethical implications of using AI for HRM and warn about both the opportunities and challenges of it. At the same time, however, they also stress the usefulness of AI for productivity and faster HR processes and encourage pioneer use of AI to ensure that they do not lose their relevance on the market. This will be further explored as the analysis progresses. Other interesting preliminary findings that will be the object of further analysis are: the HR imaginaries about the future of AI, for example replacing human work or assisting people in their jobs, and how this impacts their trust in the technology and perception about AI bias; factors that emerged as potentially leading to bias in selection, regardless of AI, considering the particularities of the Italian job market.

5.2.5 Limitations & adaptations

The first limitation is related to adapting the observation strategy to the specific characteristics and availability of the two observed companies. In fact, with Tech Hire a need to conduct digital observations emerged as it was more convenient than observing in-person as initially planned. The structure of the workweek for Tech Hire employees made it simply impossible to conduct in-person observations. Digital observations are equally valid and valuable; however, these were shorter and generated less insights than the in-person observation conducted at Social Farm, as the observed participants were much more aware of the presence of the researcher.

A second limitation emerged in the organization of the focus group with HR students. HR is a common career path for psychology students; however, those who volunteered to participate in the focus group were motivated by their interest in AI and robotics rather than HR. This meant that the focus group with students did not revolve around the theme of HR specifically but on the use of AI for work in general. Nevertheless, participants were very engaged during the focus group and had a lively discussion about the future of AI for work which led to many insights in generational differences between people who are already working and people who are approaching the job market.

5.3 Stage 2 in Norway

5.3.1 Introduction to Norwegian fieldwork

As Stage 2 was more fieldwork focused, three field sites in total are included in this period. Interviews and observations were conducted with job seekers, HR practitioners, and AI developers. Data collected in this stage includes not only interviews but also field notes, and internal documents circulated in different field sites. Based on the preliminary findings from Stage 1, the fieldwork in Stage 2 explored the above-mentioned themes deeper and complemented the interviews by immersing the researcher herself in the daily practices. The duration of each case study was 1–2 weeks, during which the researcher would follow the participants' routine and joined in all work-related activities. Formal and informal interviews with participants were conducted during or after the working days, where the same interview guidelines as from Stage 1 were applied, but with more targeted questions

that tailored to the specific contexts. In the following sections, detailed introduction will be given to each case.

5.3.2 Case one: a regional branch of international recruitment agency

Observations were conducted in a regional office of a recruitment agency that provides human resource services and temporary staffing in addition to headhunting consultancy to other enterprises. The agency is part of one of the largest recruitment companies worldwide. Each office oversees providing services in a particular geographic, but do offer flexibility based on their availability and expertise. Each regional office is generally led by a regional manager responsible for managing 10–15 employees that have different roles: recruiting temporary/permanent positions, staffing management, and sales. Each recruiter has several customer cases; thus, they often conduct multiple recruitment processes for different customers simultaneously. They also recruit for positions in many different industries, ranging from the fishing industry to high tech companies. The recruiter follows the same procedures regardless of the position or industry they recruit for. Recruiters' tasks include searching for potential candidates, writing job descriptions, disseminating job ads, application management, interviews, and reference calls. In other words, recruiters are responsible for almost everything in the recruitment procedure, but their customers make the final decisions on whom to hire.

There is no restriction on AI usage for the recruiters from the company level, but they are informed about the risks and asked not to upload any personal or confidential information when using tools like ChatGPT. Among recruiters, AI has been used to facilitate their work, but not all recruiters use AI during the recruitment and management process. The company had previously organized several seminars and workshops to inform employees about how to use AI, and the company invited employees to share their use experiences and tips regarding AI. During the fieldwork period, the company was developing AI-powered tools internally to help employees with their work.

The BIAS researcher stayed with the regional office for 7 days, shadowing both the regional manager and a recruiter who uses AI frequently in daily work. The researcher also conducted interviews with the rest of the employees, some of whom used AI from time to time and some who never use AI in their work. Shadowing included sitting next to the recruiter and observing his work on his laptop screen. He showed how he started a new case, from searching potential candidates on LinkedIn platform to proofreading and posting job posts on different platforms. The regional manager shared her work from management level with the researcher and was asked questions from time to time. Observation notes were taken during the shadowing, and reflections were written down at the end of each day. In total, 8 interviews were conducted, and 5 days of fieldwork journal were produced during the observation stay.

5.3.3 Case two: Talent match tool

The second case was conducted in a tech startup that develops an AI-based tool that helps both HR practitioners and job seekers. The main feature of this tool is to “match” between people and job positions, with a priority on skills. It provides three main services: 1) skill-based job description writing, 2) company strategy translation toward precise skill requirements, 3) skills extraction from individual surveys. The company prioritized skill-based job description writing, whereas the other two services were used to attract more users to expand their visibility for future marketing. They build these functions based on an OpenAI API, with the European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO) framework heavily informing their work. They try to involve both job candidates and HR

practitioners in their system, to provide a skill-based recruitment community. Their targeted customers are not only HR recruiters or big companies, but also individual job seekers. It is a small startup with under 10 employees, including a CEO, CFO, CTO, and other developers and designers. During the observation period, they had just finished the product development and started collecting the user feedback. The company was still at the initial stage and frequently modified their product according to the customer feedback while fieldwork was completed. As of April 2025, they had completed development and had begun selling the product.

The fieldwork lasted two weeks, with a goal of investigating how they developed the tool and communicated with their customers. The BIAS researcher was given access to their working platform to conduct digital observations. She tested their demo and provided feedback. Additionally, it was possible to join their team-building activities after work to get to know the employees better. During the observation period, each day was spent shadowing a different developer/designer. In addition, it was possible to sit in meetings during which they discussed the company strategy and their future plans. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with all employees in the startup, in addition to other informal interviews with participants after the period of stay, during which it was possible to follow their progress and changes. In total, 8 interviews and 5 days of fieldwork journal were collected.

5.3.4 Case three: the experience of international job seekers in Norway

The final Norwegian case study focuses on the foreign job seeker community in one Norwegian city, A, and investigates their struggles and difficulties on finding a job and how AI can empower or exacerbate this process. This case study collaborated with a non-profit organization offering networking and opportunities to international job seekers. The BIAS researcher attended to the organization's kick-off event and gave a short presentation to recruit participants for this case study, resulting in 6 participants, all of whom were from non-EU/EEA countries, with an average age of 35. All of them had received higher education with at least a master's degree, and two of them are finishing their PhDs. They have all lived in city A for more than 3 years and have some working experience in Norway.

As there was no concrete site to observe their job seeking practices, most interviews and observations took place in cafes or public spaces, where they could show how they prepared for job applications. Each observation lasted around 1.5-2 hours, including a one-hour interview which was followed up with observations on their practices. The observations were conducted for two weeks in total.

5.4 Master students' theses in Norway

In Norway, BIAS has also benefited from several MA theses being written and as students have been collecting additional data for the project. These are to date the following, which will be included in the final analysis and report, D4.3:

- Two NTNU students who graduated in 2024 that studied the implementation of generative AI tools at an industry park in middle-Norway, focusing on the strategies employees chose when using these tools to enhance their workflows.
- One NTNU student who graduated in 2024 and focused on generative AI tools for telecommunication companies and how management and HR use these tools.
- An NTNU student focusing on personality and skills tests with a distinction between male/female students and students from STEM/SSH backgrounds, who will graduate in 2025.

5.5 Preliminary findings in Norway

Stage 2 found that AI was more widely used in Norway than indicated in Stage 1. AI is also more acceptable among different stakeholders, with more AI-based products being developed. From the developer side, using OpenAI model as the technical base to provide service is very common. Although AI has not been found to be applied in the organizational level for HR practitioners, many will use AI (mainly ChatGPT) in their individual work, which is being encouraged by their organizations, even absent an organization-wide strategy. However, AI usage among HR practitioners varies widely. Younger HR practitioners use AI more often and are more willing to try new skills, whereas older, more senior employees still follow the previous working habits; they may “play” with AI but not actually use any of the AI-produced output in their work. Job seekers also actively use AI to facilitate their application process. Using ChatGPT to draft cover letters, proofread Norwegian writing as well as learn the foreign language are common AI practices. AI, especially ChatGPT, has become a useful tool for all stakeholder groups to fulfill different purposes.

As ethnographic fieldwork delved deeper into different cases, the data collected also showed more details regarding hiring and recruitment. All three stakeholders identified having a proper “match” as being especially important. Except for the hard requirement (e.g. educational/professional experiences), all stakeholders stressed the importance of match between candidates and job positions. However, what constituted a “match” differed between the stakeholders. Fairness was interpreted as “best match” by AI developers in the first case study (the regional branch of an international recruiting agency), and they tried to empower both HR and job seekers community by providing the AI-based service for both sides. The traditional CV and cover letter formatting are considered outdated and easy to cause bias, so that the AI developers were trying to create a new evaluation process based on skill match to achieve fair hiring. The HR recruiters described “match” as their final goal in the hiring process. The match does not only refer to the need for candidates to meet all requirements mentioned in the job ad but also implies the “cultural fit” which is hard to clarify in texts. Job seekers also discussed a lot about the “match”, but mostly just expressed their frustration on an understanding gap between themselves and HR recruiters. When they thought they matched perfectly with the job position but did not get the job in the end, they tended to speculate that biased/discriminative decision had been generated by recruiters.

In case three, which was specially focusing on the international job seekers in the Norwegian context, the results revealed the struggles and barriers that immigrants in Norway face in society. Although all participants in this case study had received higher education in Norway, they all found it challenging to find a job. Norwegian language skill is the most frequently mentioned challenge, as most positions in Norway require certain level of Norwegian fluency which is often not required when studying in Norwegian universities. Additionally, Norwegian language skill is more than just being able to write, speak or understand Norwegian; job seekers were also expected to understand the jokes and chitchats that is highly related to the culture and more difficult to acquire due to the differences in Norwegian dialects.⁷ Another large struggle concerns visas and export control

⁷ Norwegian is known to have many different regional dialects that can differ substantially from the standard Bokmål Norwegian (or Oslo dialect) that is taught in Norwegian classes. Norwegian culture often places great importance and pride into differences in regional dialects, making it especially difficult for foreigners to understand cultural norms and expressions.

regulations that make it difficult to employ individuals from, e.g. China, Iran, or Russia without these being seen as hard restrictions or discrimination. Considering all these struggles, most job seekers expressed their frustration and discouragement not only in job seeking, but also for living in Norway— they found their treatment to be unfair while also feeling vulnerable and powerless to fight against this unfair treatment. They were optimistic but also suspicious regarding AI usage from the company side, even if AI could help in omitting human bias in the evaluation process, they felt that they would not benefit because they had difficulty reaching stages in the recruitment process where AI would actually be utilized.

5.5.1 Limitations and Adaptations

Language barriers also proved to be the most significant limitation in Norwegian fieldwork, as the BIAS researcher only speaks English while the field sites are all in Norway and people most often spoke in Norwegian. Although all participants spoke perfect English, lacking Norwegian skills made it difficult for the researcher to follow the internal meetings and small conversations. Although formal interviews for the BIAS project were conducted in English, most day-to-day practices took place in Norwegian, thus the researcher could only collect data when talking with them in English or observing their daily practices with them explaining their processes to the researcher. Nevertheless, thanks to meeting documents and notes it was still possible to understand the general topic of the meetings observed and later ask clarifying questions to the informants. The language problem was less important when conducting fieldwork with job seekers and AI developers, as most job seekers are not from Norway and the developer company was an international one that used English as their working language. One mitigation effort to include more data in Norwegian with Norwegian speakers was the inclusion of several MA theses from Norwegian-speaking students that also collected data using the BIAS interview guide. also collecting data with the same interview guide. These will be fully explored in D4.3

The other limitation encountered during the fieldwork in Norway was highly dispersed nature of the job seeking community. Firstly, job seeking is a very individual and private activity, meaning that there was not a unified “community” to do fieldwork in. Although job seekers might occasionally meet together in some organizations to seek advice or help, most of them applied for jobs by themselves. Secondly, the fieldwork on job seekers relied largely on voluntary participation from stakeholders, and people who signed up for the fieldwork came from different places.

5.6 Stage 2 in Iceland

5.6.1 Introduction to Icelandic fieldwork

Through expert interviews conducted prior to Stage 1 data collection and from the interviews and field visit during the Stage 1 data collection phase, it was determined that AI usage in Iceland was highly management focused. Participants also expressed strong sentiments about the use of AI for management purposes, particularly for monitoring and performance evaluation. Fish processing factories in Iceland were counted among the most technologically advanced in the world. The use of AI had refined fish processing and worker management had become more precise and extensive in recent. Hence, we decided to focus Stage 2 work on case studies in four fish factories to explore further how AI is used in management.

5.6.2 Case studies of the four fish factories in Iceland

For the case studies, fieldwork was conducted within 4 fish factories that employed AI automated processing, monitoring and evaluation systems for increased efficiency and productivity as well as the monitoring and evaluation of employees' performance with and without the reward of extra bonuses. Two factories employed extra bonus schemes and two did not. Of the two factories not employing extra bonus schemes, one expressed interest in considering bonus schemes, but had several reservations. Three factories were visited in April and May 2024 and the final factory was visited in October 2024. This resulted in 25 interviews, 8 with HR management (HRM) and 17 with employees along with observations of the fish processing plants within each factory. Fieldwork proceeded as follows:

- Factory 1: Observations in and interviews with 3 HRM and 4 employees in Factory 1 during one week of fieldwork,
- Factory 2: Observations in interviews with 5 employees during one week of fieldwork.
- Factory 3: Observations in and interviews with 2 HRM and 5 employees during 3 days of fieldwork
- Factory 4: Observations in and interviews with 3 employees during 2 days of fieldwork.

Factories 1 and 2 were owned by the same company.

The first day of each visit was spend observing the fish processing and monitoring systems as well as the workers working there. This began with a tour of the factories and explanations from the company of the whole process: fish being brought to the factory, processed, and then packaged for immediate sale or kept in storage for sale later. Factory 3 provided a full presentation of the factory's history and technological changes implemented over time.

Observations were conducted of employees working on each section of the processing line. Fish trimming was a particular focus of the observations, as it is primarily staffed by migrant women and was where AI monitoring technology is deployed. The AI based system scrutinizes how fast and how well employees clean and trim the fish for blood, gut, bones, worms and any defects. Each employee's performance is displayed on a screen in front of all workers and performance between workers is compared. The entire production process is observed by surveillance cameras. In addition to monitoring the production and the performance of the workers, the cameras were a security measure that allowed for immediate action should an accident occur in any part of the factory or processing line. Researchers were shown examples of the information from the fish trimming line that is displayed to managers kind of information shown to the managers from the trimming line.

Following the observations, and during subsequent days of the visit, interviews were conducted with HR/factory managers and employees. The interviews briefly explored recruitment and bias with a primary focus on AI based management, experiences of workers before and after the introduction of the highly advanced AI automated, processing, monitoring and evaluation systems. They explored the impact of AI based performance monitoring and evaluation on the well-being of workers especially in relation to stress and strain, comparison of experiences with or without the introduction of a bonus system, workers' safety and security, workers' rights, worker and organizational preparedness, workplace fairness, bias and bias mitigation as well as ways in which workers felt their working conditions could be improved.

5.6.3 Preliminary findings in Iceland

Findings indicated that employees faced a decline in wellbeing and health due to fast-paced work, the nuanced and constant mode of performance monitoring and evaluation, limited workplace interaction, competition, and, in some instances, the design of the Fish processing line itself. Employees perceived their wellbeing and health in terms of their psychological wellbeing attributed to levels of stress and strain, physical wellbeing associated with reported back, arm, neck and shoulder pain, and social wellbeing in relation to their interpersonal relations in the workplace. However, fish factory employees had both positive and negative experiences with the advent of AI-powered automated processing, monitoring and evaluation systems. Some employees felt their work had become more stressful and strenuous because they were doing 2 to 4 times more work than before and their wellbeing had declined since the introduction of the AI powered machines. They also felt the fast-paced work had reduced their ability to socialize with their colleagues. On the other hand, some employees reported that their work had become easier with no change to their wellbeing or increased wellbeing due to the switch from more manual work to a more automated work process. This included, substituting the manual carrying of heavy fish boxes, cutting of whole fish and packaging of fish with robots. For these reasons some of the employees did not prefer these technological changes while others did. Some employees mentioned language barriers and the structure of breaks as another limiting factor to workplace interaction. Previously, the trimming line stopped, and everyone took a break at the same time. Now, it runs continuously, and a screen in front of them indicates when to take a break in smaller groups.

It was observed that workplace surveillance amplified stress levels of employees even when the changes to their work processes did not cause them much stress. In addition to workplace surveillance, the introduction of extra bonus schemes that awarded higher performance bonuses to top performing employees exacerbated stress levels of employees and created more hostile and competitive working environments. When comparing the experience of employees whose performance accrued extra bonuses with those whose performance did not, the former seemed to experience more stress and complained more about their physical health. They also felt the measurement for deciding their extra bonuses was another source of stress for them as they felt the urge to work faster to avoid falling behind their colleagues. The latter admitted that should they be put on an extra bonus scheme they would equally feel more stressed. Employees felt the AI-based system did not always distribute fish equally to all workstations, although they reported their workplaces being fair. Fish factory employees seemed to have resigned themselves to their working conditions, which they felt they could not influence in any way.

In all instances, the new AI system of working was viewed as safe and secure by and for employees. Both management and employees stated that employees were offered training on how to use the new AI based system for fish processing as well as how the monitoring and evaluation occurs in the factories. All employees had a good enough understanding of this and were able to explain when asked. Interviews with HR management indicated high positivity on the part of management with the new AI powered systems as it resulted in more efficient work processes and higher productivity. Most HR managers felt that the employees' work had become easier, although they admitted that these technological changes had made the work more monotonous and mentally stressful even though it was considered less physically strenuous. They also agreed that some level of stress could be attached to the technological changes and the extra bonus schemes. In the two factories where extra bonus schemes were not in place, interviewees in HR management held similar opinions as their employees that introducing an extra bonus scheme could result in

increased stress, chaos and competition amongst employees. They all expressed interest in exploring more advanced technology and admitted that, although this may further increase productivity, efficiency and ease of work, it could also lead to redundancy. In the area of company/employees' preparedness and workers' rights, some HR managers stated that prior to adopting new technology, organizations should consider their organizational goals, cost, risk, feasibility, involvement of workers in decision-making and affording them the opportunity to try out new technologies as well as provide assistance to employees who may lose their jobs.

5.6.4 Limitations and Adaptations

Language barriers between the researchers and participants were one of the limitations. In the fish factories, a few of the employees were neither fluent in English nor Icelandic, whereas researchers could not speak the varied native languages of these employees. This made it difficult for them to express themselves in either language unlike some of their colleagues with stronger language skills who were interviewed. Thus, some important information may have been missing. Questions were asked as slowly and clearly [using simple vocabulary when necessary] with as many simple vocabularies and alternated between English and Icelandic when either language was a barrier. Another limitation was having the management of the fish factories serve as gatekeepers. They had the role of connecting the research team with the employees and decide upon whom to interview. It is unknown if and then how the management used their own criteria of inclusion or exclusion such as choosing employees that would favor the company when deciding on which employees to select for us. Our criteria specified the need for employees willing to partake in the study, with good enough proficiency in English and/or Icelandic as well as those who had experienced the technological changes their work at the factories had gone through. We ensured to ascertain that employees were there of their own accord and properly understood what the research was about as well as explain clearly their privacy in regard to the interviews and their identity, which made them feel at ease.

It can be seen as a strength of the study that the factories were willing to work with us, allowing us to conduct the interviews in the factories, during employees' working hours. At the same time, it may have created insecurity among the interviewees, and fear of being critical of the new technology, that we were present in their immediate working environment.

5.7 Stage 2 in the Netherlands

Dutch fieldwork was conducted by the two BIAS researchers who also had responsibility for Norwegian and Icelandic fieldwork. The goal of the Dutch fieldwork was to build on data collected from Norway and Iceland. It was designed to explore further the job seeker and employees' experiences, employees' rights, health and wellbeing, fairness, bias and mitigation in AI tools for recruitment and management, as well as the involvement of civil society organizations. To cover these areas, fieldwork was planned around five case studies to be conducted from October to December 2024.

Special attention was paid to four stakeholder groups in the Netherlands: AI developers/experts, HR experts, foreign job seekers, and representatives of civil society organizations. Although there were no Stage 1 interviews or observations in The Netherlands, desk research on the status quo of AI used in the labor market in the Dutch context was conducted. Assistance was sought from partners in the Netherlands who attempted to contact AI companies from the HR Technology Conference and Exposition Europe that had recently been held in Amsterdam. Additionally, companies that

participated in BIAS co-creation workshops in WP2 were contacted. Specific companies and organizations that most relevant for BIAS were identified.

5.7.1 Case one: Chinese job seekers' experience in the Netherlands

The case study on job seekers specifically focuses on the Chinese community in the Netherlands. The Chinese community is one of the biggest foreign communities in the Netherlands population wise. Ethnic Chinese is the fifth largest group of non-Western immigrants in the Netherlands (Gijsberts, Huijnk & Vogels, 2011) and China ranked third among countries of origin for international students in Dutch higher education institutions. Additionally, a BIAS researcher was from China, making it easier for her to approach and recruit participants.

The participant recruitment was conducted by making a post about the BIAS project on a Chinese social media platform that is the most popular platform among Chinese people living abroad. Information was provided through the post and people who showed interest contacting the researcher team who privately responded to these contacts. Subsequently, on-site interviews and observations were conducted during weekend or afterwork times. All fieldwork was based on individual cases, through which the researcher would meet the participant in person and spend the full morning or afternoon together. All the observations were conducted in November 2024 and five individual case studies were collected during the fieldwork. All participants had received higher education and lived in the Netherlands for at least two years.

5.7.2 Case two: AI hiring tool for fairness

A second case study planned to observe a tech company that develops an AI-based tool for hiring. The tool uses AI to analyze candidates' language use based on language features to achieve a faster, easier and fairer result. The main feature of this AI-based tool is "language evaluation" so that the HR recruiters could dispense with the use of traditional CVs or cover letters and use AI to quickly have an overview of the candidates. The representatives of the company were first approached in May 2024 at the HR tech conference, which resulted in a 5-month negotiation with the CEO and CTO regarding access to the company. One site visit to the company was conducted, during which interviews were conducted with the CTO and a salesperson. Following the visit formal approval was given for longer-term observations. This approval was withdrawn immediately before fieldwork was scheduled to begin because the company determined it was too busy to accommodate an external researcher. Although the fieldwork was not successful in the end, field notes from the single preparatory visit were still taken and used as data material for the Dutch fieldwork.

5.7.3 Case three: AI/Algorithm Based Assessment and Management Tools

A third case was planned for one of the largest mobile and internet service providers in the Netherlands, which has offices in several Dutch cities. Fieldwork was planned to observe their use of an assessment tool used in their recruitment process that heavily influenced the hiring decisions⁸ as well as an inhouse management tool in the final phases of development that would soon be deployed internally. Observations would have focused perceptions of the use of the assessment tool and perceptions of the soon-to-be introduced management tool. There were also plans to conduct fieldwork with the external company that developed the recruitment assessment tool and with an NGO that recommended job applicants with

⁸ Subsequent interviews with the company revealed that the tool was algorithm rather than AI-based

disabilities to this company. Thus, observations and interviews were to be conducted with AI/Tech experts in both developer and user companies, a CSO representative from the NGO as well as HR managers, employees and the DEI officer within the mobile and internet service company. This was to gain a holistic overview of the AI/algorithm-based assessment and management tools and cover more thoroughly the general goals of the Dutch fieldwork.

Unfortunately, the fieldwork did not go as planned. Although several attempts were made, it was not possible to gain access to the external technical development company or the NGO. Additionally, although HR managers and an AI expert were recruited at one site of the company, they were not able to secure access at any other sites.

Although the comprehensive fieldwork originally envisioned was not achieved, a BIAS researcher was able to complete three visits over a two-week period that included interviews with HR managers and an AI expert at one company work site. This included a detailed overview of candidate selection process and the assessment tool used, including explorations of the possibility of bias with this type of assessment. An additional interview explored an AI tool developed to predict employee turnover and the HR chat bot developed to assist employees with HR policy related questions. Interview questions covered developer autonomy, data usage and privacy considerations, bias and fairness in AI models, impact on employees including employees with disability, employees' preparedness, legal and ethical considerations, and the future of AI in HR.

5.7.4 Case four: Fairness in AI Tool Development, Recruitment and Management

This fieldwork was conducted with three AI experts. Two were working with one of the largest recruitment and talent management agencies in the Netherlands specializing in data analytics, ethics and AI projects related to recruitment and staffing. One was a researcher who had experience in building machine learning models and had contributed to a community-driven AI fairness project aimed at improving fairness in AI systems. The initial plan was to carry out a holistic fieldwork that included interviews, observations and document reviews with AI experts, HR experts and employees within recruitment and talent management agencies, similar to original plans for Case three. Similarly to Case three, although numerous attempts were made to get comprehensive access to the organization, it was not possible to do so beyond interviews with a few employees. Given the availability and preference of the participants, interviews were conducted online via teams. Thus, three interviews were carried out over a three-week period.

The first interview was carried out with the AI researcher. This interview explored the design of AI tools and training data sources, developer autonomy, responsible and explainable AI, AI for recruitment and management including bias in AI tools, AI for advertising, AI for interviews and performance evaluation and assessment, bias mitigation, AI ethics and responsibility of AI developers, as well as impact on workers' health and wellbeing. The interview ended with the provision of a link to the AI fairness project⁹. A follow up was done via email for contact with other AI researchers but yielded no response. The second interview was with the AI expert involved in various AI projects related to recruitment and staffing. During this interview the researcher received an overview of the organization and explored their recruitment process as a third party recruitment agency, the development of AI tools, developer autonomy and training data, bias in AI tools, ethical considerations and ethical responsibility of developers, impact on employees, the role of legislation in AI development and compliance. The interview ended with final thoughts on

⁹ See: <https://fairlearn.org/>

recommendations for organizational preparedness prior to the adoption of AI tools. The final interview with the data analyst and ethic specialist explored the establishment of a center of expertise for AI ethics within the company. It was disclosed that the company buys data from third party vendors and probing into their data purchases and its use in recruitment and management was done. The researcher further explored DEI in recruitment when using third party AI systems and bias mitigation, legislation and compliance, risk assessment and standards, employees' preparedness, rights as well as well as wellbeing and health.

5.7.5 Case five: The Perception and Role of Civil Society Organizations

This fieldwork was to gain additional insight into the roles and perception of civil society organizations on AI for HRM practices. Six interviews were conducted with representatives of civil society organizations spanning trade/labour unions at the national and European level, rights-based organizations, migrant women groups and government advisory agencies. Half of the interviews were via teams and the other half were carried out in person at the participants' various organizations from late October 2024 to early December 2024 following availability of participants. Half of the interviews had to be rescheduled due to illnesses and overlapping schedules. During these interviews the perception and role of trade unions and NGOs in AI management and bias mitigation were explored. The interviews further explored more generally perceptions of AI in recruitment and management processes, AI recruitment/management risks, bias and mitigation, AI surveillance, performance evaluation and monitoring, AI impact including impact on employees and jobseekers, employee's rights and wellbeing, (AI) legislation/regulations/frameworks and standards, as well as ethics and ethical responsibilities of stakeholders.

5.7.6 Preliminary findings in the Netherlands

In the Netherlands, it was noted that the commercialization of AI/algorithm-based applications in the labor market was relatively advanced, and the public has generally shown greater acceptance of AI use. A wide range of AI/algorithm-based products is already available on the market to support HR functions, covering everything from recruitment assistance to employee management. Productivity improvement, efficiency and ease of work are highly prioritized when deciding on AI applications in HRM. Bias mitigation and DEI support were also emphasized as selling points by some of the AI developers and motivation for purchase by some of the HR experts.

In **the planned case study with the developer company**, fairness had been interpreted as a part of evaluation criteria that avoids using CV and cover letters when selecting candidates. The traditional hiring process, where CV and cover letters are the main information source from the candidate side, has been perceived as outdated and biased. Interviewed developers believed that human beings are born with bias, and they can never make objective decisions without the help of technology. Under this thread, AI has been placed as a necessity to fulfil diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) initiatives in organizations.

The case study on foreign job seekers showed that language and visa requirements are the two main challenges for Chinese job seekers in the Netherlands. According to participants, companies favor native employees compared with internationals. Although everyone can apply for a position that requires Dutch language skill, the interviewees

believed that such requirements implied that this employer only wanted to hire Dutch people. Additionally, companies prefer to hire people with permanent residence visa—candidates are likely to be rejected if they ask for sponsorship from the company. Instead of considering these requirements as unfair, participants took this for granted. They usually compare this situation with Chinese context, saying that they will also prefer native job candidates if it was in China. Also, they thought they are too powerless to fight back individually, and that it would be a waste of time if one spent time arguing with the company instead of moving on to find another job. Typical social expectations toward Chinese job seekers were also mentioned several times by the participants, that they were expected by employers to be hardworking and buttoned-up, and to not mind a work-life balance heavily weighted towards work. Therefore, extra work would always be assigned to them, and they would be blamed if they didn't follow such social expectations.

The case study on AI/algorithm-based assessment and management tools revealed that the company's recruitment process begins with advertising or job posting on career sites and various marketing platforms like LinkedIn or Indeed. Different platforms are used for targeting specific job roles, such as Facebook and Instagram for customer service roles and Reddit for technical jobs. The company takes advice from a third party company on which platforms to post job vacancies. In relation to the assessment tool, it is a game-based tool that measures cognitive and soft skills. It is used to evaluate the fitness of jobseekers for roles based on their scores in problem solving and collaboration. Results from the tool were substituted with additional criteria such as availability and motivation to further evaluate candidates after the initial assessment. The interview process usually starts with a phone call to assess a candidate's motivation and suitability. The interview process also includes checking the candidate's CV and results of the assessment tool. This is usually the case for volume hires (like internship, low level, low skilled and less technical positions). For more corporate roles, the CV is first screened, followed by an interview and the assessment tool is used to provide additional insights. The HR managers believed that the assessment tool helped them in making informed decisions by providing valuable insights. They emphasized the need for personal oversight as crucial in the recruitment process, especially for making the final decision about who gets hired. With regards to company preparedness, the HR managers mentioned that they received training from the developer company and participated in demo sessions to understand the capabilities of the tool. Their motivation for adopting this assessment tool was linked to the company's vision and the potential of the tool to measure candidate's abilities as well as inclusivity of the assessment process which were key factors. They were unable to explain exactly how the tool ensures fair and inclusive assessments. They, however, mentioned that they check CVs after the tool assessment to ensure the tools accuracy and fairness.

The HR managers explained that their company uses an Oracle system for varied HR functions, including development tracking, salary payment and performance monitoring. They explained that the system is personalized to the needs of their company, including performance evaluation and salary slips. When discussing fairness and bias, they described fairness as giving all candidates equal opportunities regardless of age, gender or race. To them fairness includes transparency on reasons for hiring or rejection. They acknowledged that unconscious bias often exists in recruitment and mentioned efforts to balance gender representation by giving female candidates advantages for certain positions. They mentioned their company's DEI team that conducts initiatives and surveys to promote inclusivity within the organization. Although DEI strategies are mostly for internal employees, it extends to hiring practices, such as targeting the hiring of persons with disabilities (PWDs). It was explained that using too many qualifications and certifications in job ads can deter women from applying. Thus, they aim to make job ads more inclusive by

reducing the number of required qualifications and emphasizing transferable skills. They mentioned that it was a challenge to balance inclusivity with the need for specific qualifications for certain roles. In the area of ethics, they emphasized the importance of AI being inclusive and fair focusing on skills and qualification rather than personal characteristics like race or gender. Developing and user companies have a significant responsibility to ensure that AI tools are bias-free and protect candidate data, transparency. Also, clear communication about AI usage is crucial for maintaining trust and fairness. It was said that workers should have the right to challenge AI based decisions and be informed about the role of AI in their evaluation, there should be transparency, and employees should be able to understand and trust AI tools being used. They mentioned that the company was investigating the use of chatbots for employee communication. They confirmed that the company embraced innovation and was open to new technologies that could improve efficiency and work-life balance. They believed that AI tools could reduce their workload allowing for focus on more strategic tasks and that technological advancement could make work more enjoyable and efficient provided they were used thoughtfully and inclusively.

In the area of their in-house management tools, there was a tool for predicting employee turnover which was presently non active due to data issues although it provided strategic insights. However, the HR chatbot using generative AI to assist 1000's of employees with HR policy related questions was still in use. According to the AI expert, they were currently focused on developing a new prediction model for absenteeism, to predict if an employee is likely to be absent again after the second sick call within nine months. When asked about data usage and privacy considerations, it was revealed that the model uses internal data from HR systems but excludes personal data like age and gender. The importance of privacy checks and ethical considerations in developing and using AI models were emphasized. The model was said to be aimed at supporting managers in having conversations about possible health interventions before it becomes an obligatory conversation. When asked about bias and fairness in AI models, bias was explained as an unconscious assumption ingrained from personal and environmental contexts. It was said that the model aims to prevent bias by omitting personal information a person cannot control such as age and gender. It was deemed important to understand the context and factors influencing absenteeism to mitigate bias. When asked about preparedness and impact on employees, they highlighted the importance of communication with employees about the model. Employees were given the opportunity to voice their opinions and concerns about the model. The goal was to reduce absenteeism and improve employee health without causing stress or violating privacy. When asked about legal and ethical considerations, they emphasized the importance of legal and ethical checks in developing and using AI models as well as having a clear and legitimate purpose for using AI in HR practices. The future of AI in HR was seen to involve increased interaction and integration with the digital environment and that the cultural context would influence acceptance and use of AI in different regions.

The case study on fairness in AI tool development, recruitment and management revealed that the recruitment and talent management agency used AI systems in recruitment such as matching algorithms, screening tools and AI voice bots for initial candidate screening. AI systems were used in recruitment for targeted job advertising, interview scheduling and employee surveys. The development of a typical AI tool begins with the identification of a real-life or business problem, data analysis and iterative discussions with the business side, translating this problem into a machine learning problem and building a prediction model. Training data sources included resume selection tools, company specific data, structured data from CVs and profiles, and unstructured data from placements. The developer team had the freedom to propose solutions and refine them based on feedback from the business side. Concerns were raised about the ability to create

unbiased tools in recruitment due to the vague concept of a 'good employee' and the presence of unconscious and systemic biases. The pressure to build products may quickly lead to compromises in data suitability and careful consideration according to the interviewees. Some examples of given bias included resume selection models replicating past hiring patterns, and matching systems perpetuating bias based on job requirements.

Experts asserted that increased surveillance and performance evaluation in algorithmic management dehumanizes employees and leads to loss of autonomy and impacts on job satisfaction. AI had the potential to be disheartening and stressful, it could impact economic opportunities and job outcomes for individuals. The positive impact mentioned included the potential for AI to e.g. predict job demand. Emphasis was placed on the importance of privacy and legal frameworks in using data for AI tools as well as mitigating harm and ensuring transparency and accountability. AI-based assessments had a potential for bias thus it was important to set clear criteria for performance evaluations. The need for careful consideration of what is being measured and whether it aligns with job performance was emphasized. Other mitigation and DEI strategies included, involving experts of DEI, ensuring clear and unbiased evaluation criteria, relying on 3rd party bias audits, transparency, explainability and accountability in AI development and deployment. AI experts emphasized the need for interdisciplinary research and practice to address AI ethics effectively and the dual responsibility of developers to both build models and consider ethical implications. Experts mentioned the importance of evaluating the model with different stakeholders and thoroughly testing it prior to deployment, using aggregated data to avoid individual predictions and potential misuse, education for both developers and users as well as the responsibility of developers to anticipate potential misuse and take measures to prevent it.

AI experts from the recruitment agency mentioned the AI Act and GDPR as key regulations that guide their work. They acknowledged the need for legal frameworks but also noted the challenges of fully understanding and implementing these regulations. They explained the importance of staying informed about AI legislation in various countries where the agency operates. They emphasized the importance of internal guidelines and ethical principles in addition to legal requirements. In relation to risk assessments and standards, they conducted AI ethics assessment for all their AI systems, identifying risks and providing guidance on mitigation. It was mentioned that the agency had some AI principles and policy including prohibited systems and standards for content produced by generative AI. They were also developing a data governance framework to set standards for data access and management. With regards to organizational preparedness, experts advised combining technical knowledge with domain knowledge to develop effective AI tools. They emphasized the importance of having clear use cases and guidelines to avoid misuse and suggested iterative testing and user feedback to ensure the tool was understood and used appropriately. In relation to employees' preparedness, they cited the agency's training program which covers basics of AI, generative AI and responsible AI.

During the case study on the perception and role of civil society organizations (CSOs), a representative shared findings from a project conducted in seven European countries, highlighting the limited use of AI in recruitment in some regions like Eastern Europe. It was noted that higher skilled workers and those in formal economy are more likely to encounter AI in recruitment processes. Another representative explained that through research conducted by their organization, they found that a lot of Dutch companies did not use the more complex AI methods like face recognition in video interviewing etc. in their HR practice. They however more often use more basic algorithm-based systems which still poses a significant risk of bias. Examples of such basic systems were those that rate CVs

based on skill or use AI/algorithm-based assessments. According to them surveillance and performance evaluation are less common in Dutch firms but still exist. They noted software that monitors employee's web browsing and AI based assessment for performance reviews and that employers often rely on software outputs without fully understanding the potential for discrimination. CSO representatives held positive and negative views about the use and impact of AI in HRM. They discussed the benefits of AI such as its ability to handle large volumes of applications, potential to correct biases and potential to improve gender equality and diversity. They emphasized more on the negatives of AI such as bias and pointed out the opacity and lack of transparency of AI systems, AI exacerbating existing inequalities, data privacy breach, undue surveillance resulting in undue control and potential to cause employees stress and impact their mental health. They mentioned the potential for burn out and stress due to fast paced automated management systems, lack of control and autonomy. The biggest risk to bias was said to be the potential for seemingly neutral variables such as gaps in CVs to be proxies for discrimination. Another risk was biased historical data. The amazon example where AI favored young white males over females due to biased data sets was cited. They expressed that bias in AI applications is often due to human biases transferred into the system and pointed out the complexity of intersectional discrimination and the challenges of addressing it through current laws. They shared an example of a migrant woman who changed her name to a Dutch sounding one, and gained acceptance to organizations that had initially rejected her CV; the CV was the same. Personal data such as neighborhood and name could lead to recruitment bias, people with disabilities and neurodivergent persons are excluded from and disadvantaged in digital recruitment processes. Employers often outsource recruitment and performance evaluation to external parties, believing they are no longer responsible for preventing discrimination.

Mitigation strategies of bias and other impacts include the need for transparency and human control in AI decisions, the role of awareness raising and training for developers, more inclusive hiring practices, the need for companies to seek out reputable recruitment agencies and to be accountable for the impact of their AI tools on workers, ensuring diverse data sets during AI system design as well as diverse teams in the recruitment process. Employers should not rely solely on claims of software providers but continuously test and monitor their systems, and they should only input necessary data into the system and be aware of potential proxies for discrimination. AI developers can use synthetic data and proactively look for bias. They should be critical and ask detailed questions about potential biases in their system. Diversity quotas can be a useful tool but should not be the end goal. Representatives discussed the need for regular audits of AI systems, and a multidisciplinary approach in organizations to ensure comprehensive consideration of AI impacts and solutions. They also acknowledged the challenge of transparency due to the complexities of AI. They pointed out that there should be a balance between using AI for efficiency and ensuring fair and unbiased practices.

In the area of employees'/jobseekers' rights it was stated that they should be free from discrimination, be educated and trained to work with AI and be able to challenge decision outcomes. AI should be a subject of social dialogue within companies involving both management and employees. Representatives explained that work councils must be consulted when new technology was introduced. However, work councils often lack sufficient knowledge of technology which was a challenge. They raised the issue of jobseekers often facing the burden of proving discrimination. Representatives mentioned the EU AI Act as a key regulation for AI application in the workplace. The European platform workers directive was mentioned as including provisions for algorithmic management but not covering all workers. They pointed out the limitations of the AI Act and the GDPR in

addressing all forms of discrimination and bias and that it was challenging to implement effective regulations due to the contextual nature of AI tools. The challenges of compliance with multiple regulations and the need for standardization to simplify this process were also mentioned. They highlighted the need for more funding for CSOs and awareness-raising efforts and more regulations to address these issues effectively. It was also deemed crucial to enforce and implement existing regulations. Representatives highlighted the importance of transparency, human control and respect for privacy in AI standards and balancing regulation with innovation to ensure effective and ethical use of AI. They expressed concern about self-assessment by companies in relation to regulations and advocated for 3rd party assessments.

When asked about the role of CSOs, they emphasized the need for trade unions and NGOs to be aware of AI and its implication for employees and jobseekers and create awareness and campaigns to promote ethical AI practices. It was stated that trade unions should ask questions and seek explanations from management about AI usage, promote awareness and training of AI for employees' representatives and focus on informing workers about their rights. They discussed the need for trade unions and NGOs to be inclusive and represent the interests of all workers, including job seekers. Trade unions and NGOs could negotiate collective agreements with employers to establish principles of AI usage as well as advise governments on legislations and policies to address these issues and continuously monitor and check for adverse effects to prevent complacency. Consultation with work councils and collaboration between CSOs and government departments was deemed crucial for effective advocacy.

5.7.7 Limitations and Adaptations

The first limitation in the Netherlands was to get access to the field site. Although the researchers, with help from experts who lived in the Netherlands, had made extensive efforts to approach stakeholders, it was still very difficult to establish trust with stakeholders, especially AI developer and HR companies. Additionally, the "bias" theme is a sensitive topic for them as they were skeptical about the fieldwork and may speculated that the research could generate negative outcomes that might harm the companies. Because of these obstacles the researchers changed their strategies for the fieldwork accordingly.

5.8 Shared preliminary findings on similarities and differences in stage 2 countries

These are the preliminary findings comparing the countries.

- Increasing use of ChatGPT by HR and job seekers in Norway and Italy especially
- Idea of "culture match" or "best match" based on HR company knowledge – shared by Norway and Italy and impacting foreign workers in Norway. Also, a concern raised by CSOs in the Netherlands
- Shared issues with language in Norway, the Netherlands and Iceland – language barrier for job seekers or workers, also affecting their wellbeing, but taken for granted in the Netherlands. Language pertaining to job ads further emphasized in the Netherlands. Language issues also present in Italy but taken for granted.
- Common understanding of AI for increased efficiency / productivity / time gain.
- Perception of AI: AI as a helpful support tool rather than a decision-maker, especially at the individual level.

- Traditional hiring material like CVs and cover letters are seen as inherently biased as they contain personal data and AI is considered as a potential solution to tackle it in Italy, the Netherlands and Norway.
- Different degrees of AI integration
 - The Netherlands has the most commercialized and mature AI market in HR with both complex and basic algorithm-based systems being used.
 - Norway shows growing individual-level AI adoption, even when not organizationally mandated.
 - Italy highlights the limitations of AI, especially around contextual knowledge.
 - Iceland is unique in its factory-focused automation, dealing more with physical labor and management-based AI than HR/recruitment AI.

5.9 Transitioning from stage 2 & 1 data collection to data analysis

As all data collection, both from Stage 1 and Stage 2, has now been completed—WP4 will focus on data analysis for the remainder of BIAS, combined with knowledge exchange events to other WPs of the project (primarily with the technical work in WP3 and capacity building in WP5).

For the data analysis we present in the following section our analytical framework, as well as the preliminary coding done to date for when this report is delivered. We then describe how most of the data analysis will take place for the remainder of WP4's work leading up to the final report D4.3 due in April 2026.

6 Analytical framework

This part comprises the analytical overview happening as a third stage of the qualitative SSH research done in WP4. The full analysis is the subject of deliverable D4.3. Here we present the overall analysis strategy, steps, and preliminary findings, which will be fully explored in the final stage of WP4, subject to the final reporting in D4.3 to come.

6.1 Overall analytical framework

6.1.1 Case studies

The case study method is a research strategy commonly used in the social sciences and humanities to provide a detailed and comprehensive analysis of complex social issues. It involves examining phenomena within real-life contexts and utilizes various data collection techniques, such as interviews, observations, and document analysis. A case study typically focuses on a single case or a small number of cases, which may include individuals, groups, organizations, or communities. This approach captures social dynamics in natural settings, offering valuable insights into behaviors, institutions, and events (see e.g. Creswell, 2013). In our cases we look at how employees and managers work with AI technology by observing and interacting with people in their work environments. By watching work performance and interaction with AI tools, we aim to build on the knowledge gained from interviewees in Stage 1, furthering our understanding of the employees' and managers' behaviors and how the technology is used in practice. We also interview employees and managers at their workplace and get their views on the AI tools and how they affect work performance. We take field notes about interactions, behaviors, and the environmental context.

6.1.2 Thematic analysis and grounded theory

Thematic analysis is an established method in qualitative research which allows researchers to identify, analyze and report patterns within data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis is a method, not a methodology, in that it is not theoretically bound, therefore, it allows for flexibility and adaptation to a research's scope. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is the focus on researcher's subjectivity in identifying themes, which are not seen as emerging from the data but are co-constructed between the researcher and the data materials. Thematic analysis is not a unified method but has different variations, such as reflexive thematic analysis, coding reliability, and codebook approaches (Braun & Clarke, 2022).

For our purposes, the codebook approach was identified as the most suitable. The codebook approach, like the name suggests, centers around the development of a codebook which can give structure to the data analysis (Roberts et al., 2019). This codebook, however, is not expected to comply with the standards of coding reliability imposed by other methods but rather encourages and values researchers' subjectivity. For our project the codebook was developed inductively, after data familiarization, and combines descriptive and conceptual codes. The codebook is not fixed but provides a frame which is continuously refined through application to the whole dataset. This facilitates coding of large datasets involving many researchers while allowing for flexibility of code development.

One type of thematic analysis is **grounded theory**. Grounded theory is a qualitative research method aimed at developing theories grounded in the data, involving the inductive analysis to construct hypotheses and theories. Rather than starting with hypothesis or theoretical framework, researchers begin with questions or just the qualitative data. Through iterative coding that is open, axial, and selective, researchers will identify key

themes and categories from the data. Grounded theory is particularly valuable for exploring social processes and generating theory in areas with limited prior research. Its emphasis on participants' perspective highly supports context-rich insights (Charmaz, 2006; Glaser & Strauss, 1967).

Coding in grounded theory is the key analytical process to organize and interpret data. It begins with open coding, where researchers break data into discrete parts and label them to identify initial categories. Then axial coding is applied to connect codes and sort out relationships between categories and subcategories. Finally, selective coding integrates and refines the core categories that represent the central theme of the study. The whole process is iterative and comparative, allowing researchers to stay close to the data while developing theoretical insights (Corbin & Strauss, 2015). The coding process is both systematic and creative, echoing with thematic analysis in the previous paragraph.

The data collected during Stage 2 includes interviews, observations and field journaling. The communities studied encompass HR practitioners, job seekers, and AI developers. Given the diversity of our data sources and the cutting-edge nature of the cases explored in this stage, grounded theory emerges as our preferred analytical approach. We apply grounded theory in our collaborative data analysis process. Initially, we will review all materials to identify preliminary categories, shared codes across stakeholder groups, and specific codes unique to each group. Multiple rounds of meetings will be held to conduct axial coding and to examine the relationships among the identified categories. Subsequently, we will finalize the core categories and further investigate the central themes of our study from multiple stakeholder perspectives.

Traditional grounded theory methods can fall short for large-scale analysis due to the emphasis on inductive immersion and saturation. In response to that, an abductive approach is also considered in the data analysis process. Abductive coding secures analytical attention also to data observations that fall outside of the main categories in inductive coding and implies that we will direct analytical attention towards surprising or anomalous data (Timmermans & Tavory, 2012).

In line with the iterative process in grounded theory, the abductive approach follows a process of revisiting data, but with a stronger emphasis on seeking out novel insights learning from existing literature and theories (i.e on bias) during the coding process. Vila-Henninger et al. (2022) operationalize the framework into a three-step coding process: (1) generating an abductive codebook, (2) abductive data deduction through code equations (combinations of codes used to capture complex phenomena that span individual codes), and (3) In-depth abductive qualitative analysis. Abductive coding is beneficial when there is a need to combine theories (see Section 6.3) and when collaborating research teams drawing on different bodies of literature in their approach to the main research question (Vila-Henniger et al. 2022). To be successful abduction requires researchers to have a strong familiarity with existing theories to recognize surprising findings and develop innovative theoretical contributions, and for this purpose we build on the literature reviews conducted in the project so far.

6.1.3 Our qualitative SSH analytical framework

BIAS' qualitative analytical framework combining grounded theory with thematic analysis is summarized in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Qualitative analytical framework, figure created by the research team.

With the completion of qualitative data collection in Stage 1, leading to Stage 2 case developments, our analytical process primarily consists of the well-established methods of thematic coding, where codes are tested, verified, and, if needed, changed according to the data added to them. Theoretical sampling in this process means testing codes on new data, to see whether our big picture ideas work, leading to building an understanding of the themes we have investigated. Memo writing in this model is important for the thematic occurrences that constitute different codes in our material.

6.2 Initial analytical phase until 31/3/2025

Qualitative data analysis is a gradual process that happens as data is being gathered, which has also been the case for the analysis in WP4. Following the conclusion of the data gathering in December 2024 (with one small data gathering in Italy in February 2025) which marked the end of the Stage 2 final data collection, the analytical phase has, however, accelerated. Although data analysis was continuously discussed in WP meetings, consortium meetings, and supervision meetings with the respective PhD students prior to this date, January 2025 marked the start of the main analytical phase of the WP in the project. The following steps were taken:

6.2.1 (Initial) codebook

Applying a grounded theory approach to thematic analysis, we have opted for a codebook analysis approach which combines the structure of coding reliability approaches (Braun & Clarke, 2022) with the theme development processes of grounded theory (Corbin & Strauss, 2015). To do so, we gathered in one document all the codes that had already been identified during the analysis of Stage 1 interviews and some of Stage 2 fieldwork from the three PhDs. During a three-hour online coding workshop, the PhD candidates compared codes and grouped them by similarity in a Miro board, also dividing them by stakeholder into “shared”, “HR”, “workers”, and “AI developers”. To further refine these top-level codes and agree on their interpretation, the PhD candidates collaboratively coded three interviews: one with a job seeker in Norway, one with an HR practitioner in Italy, and one with an AI developer in Iceland. The variety of participants and profiles included in the research required a reflection on the themes that could emerge in all interviews but also in each stakeholder’s interview. Based on the coding of these three interviews, which resulted in the generation of many child-codes (or sub-codes), the main codebook was further developed and shared with the whole WP4 team for feedback and input.

The following step consisted in discussing the top-level codes with the WP4 team during an in-person coding workshop which also made use of the Miro board. The outcome of this process has been a shared codebook consisting of sixteen top-level codes which we believe capture the main themes emerged during the data collection. The focus of this process has

been that of agreeing on top-level codes, while child-codes will be identified and expanded during the coding process following a grounded-theory approach. These top-level codes will guide the coding process, however, they will be continuously refined and developed as the coding process progresses. In addition, despite the initial division between “shared”, “HR”, “workers” (including workers’ representatives and CSO representatives), and “AI developers”, due to the possibilities allowed by the data analysis software it was decided to abandon this division in the codebook. Differences between stakeholders will, however, be considered in the analysis. The figure below shows a bird-eye view of the coding process in the web-program MIRO, in March 2025, where top-level codes and child node codes had been sorted into categories.

Figure 2: Overview of Codes in MIRO

6.2.2 Setup of codebook with qualitative data analysis software’s collaborative cloud

In order to provide a thorough robust coding of all the data from WP4’s extensive data collection, and as described in the project description, we set up a codebook in a qualitative data analysis software called NVIVO, with an extension called “collaborative cloud” which enables the research team to access multi-user coding capabilities.

Following a technical delay from the university purchaser and several issues on the technical setup, (see Table 4 on the issues with mitigation steps), the NTNU team gained full access on 1. March 2025, with University of Iceland gained access 1. April 2025.

6.3 Our theoretical framework for SSH Bias research

To analyze how bias emerges and operates in AI-driven recruitment and management processes, BIAS draws upon four key theoretical frameworks from Social Science and Humanities (SSH) research: Actor-Network Theory (ANT), Domestication Theory, Intersectionality and Surveillance Theory. These perspectives offer complementary insights into how AI management tools function within broader social, technological, and institutional contexts. Rather than treating AI recruitment as a purely technical process, these frameworks allow us to examine how technology is shaped by human decisions,

organizational structures, ideologies and systemic inequalities. By applying ANT, Domestication Theory, Intersectionality, and Surveillance Theory, BIAS will explore the roles of various actors in AI hiring, how AI tools are adopted and adapted in practice, and how bias affects different social groups in intersectional ways. Actor-Network Theory (ANT) and the Role of Actors in AI Recruitment and Management

Actor-Network Theory (ANT), developed by Bruno Latour (1997; 2005) and Michel Callon (1986), provides a relational perspective on AI recruitment and management systems by mapping the interactions between human and non-human actors within networks. ANT challenges traditional distinctions between technology and human agency, instead arguing that technological systems, institutional rules, and human actors form networks that collectively influence decisions (Law, 1992). From an ANT perspective, AI recruitment and management systems do not operate in isolation; they are part of a dynamic web of interactions between various stakeholders, including:

- AI developers and engineers, who design the algorithms, determine the data inputs, and define fairness parameters.
- HR professionals and recruiters, who interpret AI-generated hiring recommendations and make decisions about whether to follow, override, or modify algorithmic outputs.
- Legal frameworks and corporate policies, which set regulatory constraints and shape how AI tools must comply with anti-discrimination laws and ethical guidelines.
- Job applicants, who engage with AI-driven hiring platforms, navigating and responding to automated assessment tools, resume screening systems, and digital interviews

AI recruitment and management tools are marketed as neutral decision-makers, but ANT reveals how their development, deployment, and effects are co-produced by social, technical, and institutional forces (MacKenzie & Wajcman, 1999). By applying ANT, this study will examine how AI bias is distributed across a network of actors, rather than being the product of a single flawed algorithm.

6.3.1 Domestication Theory and the Adoption of AI in Hiring and Management

While ANT allows us to focus on how AI recruitment systems are structured as networks of human and non-human actors, Domestication Theory shifts the focus to how technology is integrated, adapted, and contested within organizations and workplaces (Silverstone & Haddon, 1996). This perspective highlights that AI tools are not simply adopted as neutral systems—they are actively shaped by human users and organizational cultures (Haddon, 2006).

AI recruitment and management technologies are often presented as objective, data-driven solutions, but Domestication Theory suggests that technology's role is negotiated in practice (Oudshoorn & Pinch, 2003). This framework will allow us to explore questions such as:

- How do HR professionals and recruiters integrate AI tools into their existing hiring and management practices?
- Do organizations fully automate their hiring and management processes, or do they maintain human oversight to counterbalance algorithmic decisions?
- How do job applicants adjust their strategies in response to AI-driven assessments, such as modifying resumes for automated screening or adapting behavior in AI-interview settings?

- Are there workarounds, modifications, or resistance strategies that HR professionals or job seekers use to challenge, manipulate, or bypass AI decision-making?

Domestication Theory emphasizes that AI hiring tools undergo a process of negotiation, reinterpretation, and resistance, which influences their impact in real-world hiring settings (Selwyn, 2012).

6.3.2 Surveillance Theory.

Surveillance theories provide a framework for understanding workplace monitoring, viewing technological tools as instruments for oversight, discipline, and control. These theories draw on Bentham's Panopticon and Foucault's concept of disciplinary power, where individuals internalize surveillance, promoting self-regulation and reducing the need for external enforcement. David Lyon (1993) extended this idea to electronic surveillance, highlighting its invisible yet pervasive nature. With AI, monitoring has become more precise, enabling comprehensive data collection, interpretation, and prediction (Mettler, 2024). Shoshana Zuboff (2019) addresses this as surveillance capitalism which produces and relies on algorithms but is not the same as algorithms or technology in general. Surveillance capital reflects a logic, it "commands the digital milieu and directs our trajectory toward the future" (2019, 16). The shift to surveillance intensifies scrutiny on employees, shifting power from ownership of production to control over personal development and behavior (Haggerty, 2006).

Historically, surveillance targeted the underclass through human agents, but digital technologies now track "data doubles"—aggregated digital profiles (Galic et al., 2017). AI-driven monitoring abstracts surveillance into numerical assessments, transforming employees into "coded figures" whose actions are quantified. This algorithmic control can reduce autonomy, heighten job demands, and increase burnout (Maslach & Leiter, 2008). Goodhart's Law further suggests that workers optimize behavior to meet predefined metrics, often at the cost of broader well-being (Treem et al., 2023).

These theories suggest research questions such as:

- How does AI-driven workplace surveillance influence employee self-regulation and autonomy?
- What are the impacts of algorithmic management on employees' well-being and productivity?
- In what ways does the concept of "data doubles" reshape traditional employer-employee power dynamics?
- How do employees adapt their behavior in response to AI-driven performance metrics, and what are the unintended consequences?
- What ethical and legal challenges arise from the use of AI in workplace surveillance, and how can they be addressed?

6.3.3 Intersectionality and Bias in AI Recruitment

In addition to examining how AI recruitment operates as a sociotechnical system (ANT) and how it is adapted in practice (Domestication Theory), BIAS will also apply an Intersectionality framework to analyze who is most affected by algorithmic bias. Intersectionality, a concept developed by Kimberlé Crenshaw (1989), provides a critical lens for understanding how multiple dimensions of inequalities (e.g., based in race, gender, disability, class) and how these dimensions intersect to shape discrimination and inequality (Hill Collins, 2000).

Intersectionality was originally coined to describe the structural particularity of how black women were marginalized, compared to white women and black men (Crenshaw 1989), and has later been applied to explore how a variety of social inequalities are entangled and create specific situations of suppression (i.e Lutz et al., 2011, Nach & Pinto, 2023). As a theoretical perspective, intersectionality addresses power dynamics and systemic inequalities and provides a framework for linking individual experiences to analysis of structural dynamics (Cole 2023, Nash 2023).

Categories of difference such as "race", "ethnicity", "disability", are fluid and context-dependent, varying across time and place, shaped by power dynamics, in sociometrical relations. The meaning and significance of any difference are, therefore, not inherent. As pointed out by Mahadevan et al. (2023) it is important for research to recognize the agency of individuals to resist and subvert these structures, challenging dominant narratives and redefining difference in the process. We will for that reason apply the theoretical perspective as outlined by Marfelt (2016), in line with grounded theory and abductive analytical strategies to enhance the understanding of how inequalities are potentially reinforced or mitigated.

AI-driven tools have been shown to reproduce existing inequalities in the labor market, with disproportionately negative effects on historically marginalized groups (Benjamin, 2019). This study will explore how bias in AI hiring and management manifests across different social identities, asking questions such as:

- In what manner does AI recruitment systems reinforce gender biases, such as prioritizing male candidates in technical and leadership roles based on historical hiring data? (Dastin, 2018)
- How do AI-driven facial recognition and speech analysis tools disproportionately impact non-white candidates due to racial biases in training datasets? (Buolamwini & Gebru, 2018)
- How are AI hiring tools designed with assumptions about communication, behavior, or professional presentation that disadvantage neurodivergent job seekers or individuals with disabilities? (Scholz, 2020)
- In what way do AI recruitment platforms systematically filter out candidates from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, for example, by ranking applicants based on prestigious universities or corporate job histories? (Crawford, 2021)
- What effect, if any, does AI-driven workplace monitoring, designed to enhance efficiency, productivity, and performance, have on employees' psychosocial and physical well-being? (Christenko et al., 2022).
- In what manner does AIWM technology worsen inequalities in the workplace for already marginalized employees, (Benjamin, 2019) or does it help make it more equal?

By using Intersectionality as an analytical framework, this study will examine how different social categories overlap and compound the effects of AI hiring and management bias (Eubanks, 2018).

6.3.4 Combining theoretical strands

As described in the introduction to this report, the SSH analysis stage is based primarily in the two scientific fields of the two university partners whose departments are participating in the project:

- Sociology, University of Iceland

- Science and Technology Studies (STS), particularly a feminist technoscience lens, NTNU

From these disciplines, we apply a theoretical model built on the following theoretical approaches:

- Actor-Network Theory (ANT)
- Domestication of technology theory
- Surveillance theory
- Intersectionality theory

Our plan is for the remaining of the project, especially leading up to the final WP4 report D4.3 of April 2026, to build and combine these theories in a robust project framework that can shed new insight on the analytical findings, seeing new combinations and understandings of our data.

7 Conclusions

The qualitative social science and humanities research conducted in WP4 of the bias project can be seen as a three-stage process. Stage 1 consisted of the definition of the study protocol and qualitative interviews with developers, employers and employees impacted by AI in the workplace. This has been reported on in deliverable D4.1 followed by Stage 2, which primarily concerns this present deliverable D4.2 which constitutes the second half of the data materials gathered. The data collection primarily occurred in autumn 2024 followed by the beginning of the larger analytical phase of the data. The final analytical overview with findings, as well as the transfer to the technical WP3 and the capacity building WP5, is the subject of the future deliverable D4.3 which will be submitted in April 2026.

Stage 1 found that the use of AI for recruitment and management in Europe is multifaceted, which called for more in-depth studies of how these processes happen in practice. For the final Stage 2 of the data collection, where our data collectors went more in-depth into the different cases with site visits, more inspired by ethnographic approaches to qualitative data collection, we followed a research design of grounded theory combined with thematic analysis, built on separate case studies in four different countries: Norway, the Netherlands, Iceland and Italy. The rich data material has yielded important key findings, which will for the final third stage of the qualitative SSH work in WP4 both inform the technical work in WP3 and the capacity building work in WP5, as well as yield novel insight as SSH findings through WP4. These preliminary key insights are:

7.1 Key insights

In **Italy**, there is an increasing use of AI for recruitment. HR practitioners are generally aware of the risks of AI bias and for this reason know to avoid using historical data and to oversee AI's decisions. AI becomes a support for searches with a high number of CVs or for very specific ones, but it is not used for the final decision making. HR practitioners value human contact during the recruitment process and trust their sensibility in avoiding bias. This trust in their “gut feeling” can be a sign of experience but it can also hide biases. Knowing the context in which the candidates will be hired is considered fundamental for making a good recruitment decision, this kind of contextual knowledge is, however, difficult to communicate to AI. Expectations about the future role of AI in HR are intertwined with expectations about work and the HR role and the activities they perceive as intrinsically human.

In **Norway**, AI is widely used by HR practitioners and job seekers at the individual level. AI has become a popular infrastructure for developers to integrate in the current services they provide. AI for DEI is an important topic in the Norwegian context, and people are aware of the ethical issues that AI may bring to the hiring practices. In general, people are optimistic about the future of AI and emphasize the awareness of ethics in all cases. Although HR practitioners stressed that they have worked hard to tackle the subjects of fairness and bias, racial and ethnicity bias were still perceived to be prevalent by job seekers. However, it is difficult to definitively identify bias and discrimination during the hiring process as it mixes with qualifications and other culture and socially “matching” ideas. Even if job seekers were aware that discrimination existed in their cases, they described feeling powerless to fight back due to the imbalanced power relationship and high money and/or time cost. In the development of AI based tools to tackle bias and achieve fairness, fairness has been interpreted and operationalized in diverse ways. Especially in the function where AI is used to evaluate candidates, fairness has been interpreted as finding the “perfect match” between candidates and the job positions.

In **Iceland**, high-tech fish processing companies utilized AIWM to gather real-time data on the productivity and quality of work among employees on the trimming line. Most of these workers were foreign women. They did not openly object to having a screen in front of them displaying their performance compared to their colleagues, and they felt they had no choice but to accept this monitoring. However, the real-time data turned out to be a significant source of stress for many, particularly for those who earned individual bonuses based on this AI based collection of information.

In **The Netherlands**, HR practitioners usually receive many CVs for each position that needs to be filled, so it is very common for them to use digital tools (with and without AI functions) to increase efficiency during the hiring process. The commercialization of AI and/or algorithm-based systems used in hiring and recruitment is very advanced, and developers have launched AI tools for different purposes. With regards to bias and discrimination, companies tend to prefer hiring native citizens rather than foreigners. Although not explicitly mentioning this preference in the job ad, many companies use Dutch to write job descriptions, implying the demands of Dutch language skill and exclusion of non-Dutch speakers. While HR and AI experts seemed to embrace more easily the use of AI in HRM, CSO representatives were more critical of such use. CSO representatives outlined the many negative impacts of AI on employees and jobseekers alike, advocating for employees'/jobseekers' rights and ethical responsibility of developer and user organizations. All participants were aware of the issue of bias and provided recommendations for addressing it. Biased historical data and other training data sources as well as human biases are more commonly identified as high-risk to produce or reinforce AI bias. The potential for neutral variables to be proxies for discrimination (eg. Length of work experience can be a proxy for age discrimination even if age or birthdate is removed from the application. Information on education/graduation from an all-women's university can be a proxy for gender discrimination) is of critical importance to note and further study as this has the potential to lead to bias even in systems designed to mitigate bias, given that such variables can easily be overlooked (eg. Address or postcode). Although there were complaints about the challenges of implementing regulations, the need for more regulations and implementation of existing ones were also emphasized as necessary.

For the final analysis, please refer to D4.3 planned for April 2026.

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